

M.ENG EXTERNAL DEFENCE

ON

ROTOR ANGLE STABILITY ANALYSIS OF A GRID-CONNECTED RENEWABLE
ENERGY SOURCE

BY

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NDA/PGS/FE/EEE032020/P05943

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JUNE, 2023.

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this thesis has been conducted by me under the supervision of Dr. Aliyu Sabo. Department of Electrical/Electronic Engineering, Nigerian Defence Academy, Kaduna. Authors whose works have been referred to in this thesis have been duly acknowledged.

Odoh, Theophilus Ebuka.

Date

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that the Master of Engineering thesis titled “ROTOR ANGLE STABILITY ANALYSIS OF A GRID-CONNECTED RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCE” by ODOH THEOPHILUS EBUKA (NDA/PGS/FE/EEE032020/P05943) meets the requirements for External Defence.

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DEDICATION

This thesis is dedicated to God almighty.

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ABSTRACT

Rotor angle stability analysis is crucial in identifying and controlling electromechanical oscillations in the power system. These oscillations can result in loss of generator synchronism and power flow disruption. A single-machine infinite bus (SMIB) model was developed in *MATLAB*[®] software to investigate rotor angle stability, following a large disturbance in the SMIB system brought about by a simulated three-phase fault. The SMIB generator rotor speed deviation response reaches a settling time of 9.94 seconds. A proposed Power system stabilizer (PSS) damping controller, optimized using the Artificial ecosystem algorithm (AEO) was able to control the generator rotor speed deviation to 1.89 seconds settling time. The proposed controller was validated by comparing it to genetic algorithm optimized PSS at 2.20 seconds settling time and particle swarm optimized PSS at 2.15 seconds settling time. Furthermore, a doubly fed induction generator (DFIG) was integrated into the SMIB system and the proposed Artificial ecosystem-optimized PSS damping controller was able to control the generator rotor speed deviation to 2.5 seconds settling time. The results showed that the proposed Artificial ecosystem-optimized PSS damping controller was able to control electromechanical oscillations in a single-machine infinite bus system and also in a single-machine infinite bus integrated with a doubly fed induction generator (DFIG) system which leads to improved power system stability.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

PSS	Power system stabilizer
SMIB	Single machine infinite bus
Matlab	Matrix laboratory
AEO	Artificial ecosystem optimization
PSO	Particle swarm optimization
GA	Genetic algorithm
DFIG	Doubly fed induction generator
WECS	Wind energy conversion system

EESG	Electrically excited synchronous generator
SCIG	Squirrel cage induction generator
PMSG	Permanent magnet synchronous generator
MSC	Machine side converter
GSC	Grid side converter
AVR	Automatic voltage regulator
CPU	Central processing unit
DAE	Differential algebraic equation
EMs	Electromechanical modes

list of mathematical notations

δ	Generator rotor angle	H_t	Turbine inertia
ω_s	Synchronous Speed	H_g	Generator inertia
H	Inertia constant	K_{tg}	Drive train shaft stiffness
D	Self-damping	C_{tg}	Drive train damping coefficient
E_{fd}	Field voltage	w_{elB}	Electrical base speed
R_s	Armature resistance	R	Length of turbine blades
ψ_{1d}	Sub-transient EMF due to flux linkage in d-axis	C_p	Power coefficient of the blades
I_d	d-axis component of stator current	β	The pitch angle of the blade
V_d	d-axis component of generator terminal voltage	λ	Tip speed ratio
x_d, x'_d, x''_d	Synchronous, transient, and sub-transient d-axis reactances	P_t	Mechanical power output
T'_{d0}, T''_{d0}	Transient and sub-transient d-axis open-circuit time constants	w_t	Turbine rotational speed

K_a	Static excitation gain	w_{trated}	Turbine rated speed
E_t	Generator voltage magnitude	w_g	Generator speed
T_g	Time constant of the governor	θ_{tg}	Shaft twist angle
R_{gov}	Governor droop	T	Torque (subscripts g, s, t refer to generator, shaft, and turbine)
ω_r	Rotor angular speed	L_m, L_s	Mutual and stator inductance
ω_b	Base value of speed	C_{dc}	Capacitance
T_m	Mechanical torque	R_s, R_r	Stator and rotor resistance
T_e	Electrical torque	V_{dc}	Capacitor voltage
E'_q	Transient EMF due to flux linkage in q-axis damper coil	L_i	Inverter-side inductance
x_{ls}	Armature leakage reactance	R_i	Inverter-side resistance
ψ_{2q}	Sub-transient EMF due to flux linkage in q-axis damper	L_g	Grid-side inductance
I_q	q-axis component of stator current	R_g	Grid-side resistance
V_q	q-axis component of generator terminal voltage	C_f	Filter capacitor
x_q, x'_q, x''_q	Synchronous, transient, and sub-transient q-axis reactances	R_c	Damping resistance
T'_{q0}, T''_{q0}	Transient and sub-transient q-axis open circuit time constant	P_s, P_r	Stator and rotor active power
T_a	Static excitation time constant	Q_s, Q_r	Stator and rotor reactive power
v_{ref}	Excitation voltage reference	P_{msc}	Active power flowing through MSC
T_{m2}	Generation load reference	P_{gsc}	Active power flowing through GSC

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Recent power grid systems to meet energy demand and overcome concerns about climate change are massively integrated with renewable energy sources. In developing countries such as Nigeria, the author in [1] notes that power supply authorities have been struggling to meet energy demand to no avail due to heavy demand. This renewable energy source consists of power electronics control devices that allow a very short time for reaction, this time could be below one second, and new technologies [2]. Thus, the author in [3] expresses the idea that the power grid system forms a very big artificial living network.

With the increased renewable energy integration into the power grid system, areas of generation are exposed to electromechanical oscillations. These oscillations have been observed in many power grids worldwide. The electromechanical oscillations may be local, that is, a generator against all the power system grid components, or inter-area, which is the electromechanical oscillation between a group of generators distributed over a wide geographical area [4]. Uncontrolled electromechanical oscillations may lead to total power disruption known as grid collapse.

Over the years, most power system engineering studies related to large and small oscillations were known as transient and steady-state stability respectively. With increased generator interconnection and renewable energy integration, a new phenomenon that results from a continuous small-signal buildup of electromechanical oscillations began to appear. One recent example is the nationwide power outage in Sri Lanka on December 3, 2021 [5], which was caused

by electromechanical oscillation between the two power-generating stations in the Kotmale-Anuradhapura area.

Time domain simulations and electromechanical mode analysis are used to study how the power grid system responds to small signals. Power system stabilizers (PSS) are commonly used to damp and control local and inter-area oscillation modes, with an increase in transmission line loading and operating conditions as a result of renewable energy integration. The parameters of the PSS damping controller have to be optimally tuned with an optimization algorithm in line with the new operating conditions. Since power grid systems are highly non-linear, that is the power system operating conditions can fluctuate over a wide range of operations [6]. Conventional fixed parameters of the PSS damping controller cannot cope with the wide operating range. PSS damping controller when designed with an optimization algorithm is observed to be an effective means for damping electromechanical oscillations [7].

The wind energy industry has grown a lot and is now considered to be a very mature industry. These days, wind power of thousands of megawatts distributed over an extensive area is integrated into the grid. The wind turbine's performance is affected by disturbances in the grid, which cause electromechanical oscillations [8]. Thus, with increased wind penetration, there is a need to develop models and test systems that convert wind energy and study the impact of their integration into the grid.

1.2 Problem statement

The wind generation system's impact on the overall operation of the power grid system can no longer be ignored if significant integration levels are to be achieved. It is critical to maintain the power grid system stability while improving its generation capacity. The inherent

electromechanical oscillations in the generator must be damped to maintain a stable power grid. Failure to damp these oscillations can result in the power grid's loss of synchronization, leading to power supply disruption and economic loss. PSS damping controllers are commonly used to damp the oscillations [6], [9], but conventional fixed parameters of PSS damping controllers cannot cope with the continuous fluctuation of power grid operating conditions. Therefore, optimization techniques are adopted in PSS design, and metaheuristic optimization algorithms are often used due to their high computational efficiency [10]–[12].

1.3 Aim and Objectives

This research aimed to study the rotor angle stability of a grid-connected renewable energy source.

Through the following objectives, the research aim was achieved:

- i. A single machine connected to an infinite bus system (SMIB) was designed in Matlab/Simulink which represents the conventional power grid system.
- ii. An optimized PSS damping controller using the artificial eco-system (AEO) optimization method for the SMIB power test system, and the validation of the PSS damping controller performance when compared to PSS damping controllers designed with metaheuristic algorithms which include; genetic algorithm (GA) and particle swarm optimization (PSO) as well, this damping controller is used to control electromechanical oscillation and maintain stability before renewable energy is introduced.
- iii. A Doubly fed Induction generator (DFIG) which represents the wind energy renewable conversion system designed in Matlab/Simulink and integrated into the

single machine connected to an infinite bus system with an optimized AEO PSS damping controller.

1.4 Methodology

The methodology involved modeling the SMIB power test system, designing a PSS damping controller for it, simulating a Three phase fault on the SMIB power test system, and conducting rotor angle stability analysis. The proposed AEO optimization algorithm was compared with GA and PSO optimization techniques in PSS damping controller design. Lastly, the DFIG wind energy conversion system was integrated into the SMIB power test system, and an AEO PSS damping controller was proposed for the integrated system.

1.5 Scope of the Study

The scope of this research is as follows:

- i. A Power System Stabilizer (PSS) damping controller design adopting the Artificial Ecosystem Optimization (AEO) for effective damping of electromechanical oscillations in the power grid system.
- ii. Evaluation of the effectiveness of the proposed PSS damping controller design approach by comparing it with other optimization techniques, such as Genetic Algorithm (GA) which is a metaheuristic algorithm, and Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) as well.
- iii. Validation of the PSS damping controllers using simulation studies of a Single machine connected to an infinite bus and a Doubly Fed Induction Generator Wind renewable Energy Conversion System (DFIG-WECS) integrated into the SMIB power test system model

1.6 Significance of the study

This study's significance is highlighted below:

- i. This research will provide an understanding of wind energy integration's impact on the power system grid and the need to damp electromechanical oscillations to maintain power system stability.
- ii. The study will provide insights into optimization technique operations, especially the Artificial Ecosystem Optimization (AEO) algorithm, in designing Power System Stabilizers (PSS) damping controllers in the power grid system.
- iii. The results of this research will be beneficial to power grid system operators, planners, and engineers, as it will provide a reliable PSS damping controller which when adopted can improve the overall stability and control of the power grid system.
- iv. This research will also help in the field of power system engineering, particularly in the area of renewable energy integration and PSS damping controller design.

1.7 Outline of thesis

This thesis is organized into five chapters.

Chapter 1 presents the introduction to the study background and the research problem statement, it also states the aim and objectives of the thesis, the methodology adopted in the research, scope, significance, and lastly the thesis outline.

Chapter 2 provides a review of fundamental concepts related to rotor angle stability in power systems, power system modeling of a single machine connected to an infinite bus, wind energy conversion system represented by a Doubly fed induction generator, and PSS damping controller design for rotor angle stability analysis. A comprehensive review of similar works and also the research gap is presented.

Chapter 3 presents a step-by-step modeling of the SMIB power test systems, DFIG-WECS integrated into the SMIB power test system, PSS damping controller design using an artificial ecosystem algorithm, genetic algorithm, and particle swarm optimization.

Chapter 4 focuses on studying the rotor angle instability created by simulating a fault (three-phase symmetrical fault) at 1 second on the model. This chapter also evaluates the efficiency of the proposed artificial ecosystem PSS damping controller in improving electromechanical modes and damping oscillations.

Finally, Chapter 5 presents the conclusion and recommendations for further research from results obtained from the study

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter presents an overview of the relevant literature and theoretical background related to the present study. It provides an overview of power grid system stability, specifically rotor angle control and stability, oscillations, single machine connected to an infinite bus, wind energy conversion system, damping controller design and performance, and a review of metaheuristic algorithms, artificial eco-system, and objective function formulation.

2.2 Theoretical Review of Subject Matter

Power system stability is the capacity of an electric power system, for a given initial operating condition, to return to a state of operating equilibrium following a physical disturbance, with most system variables bound so that essentially the entire system is unaffected [13]. It is an important factor to consider to ensure the power grid system works safely and reliably. The growing use of renewable energy sources like wind creates several problems that require a lot of changes to the current power grid system and threaten its security [14].

2.2.1 Power system stability and Oscillations

Though Power system stability could be considered a single problem but treating it as such makes it harder to understand and deal with the different kinds of instability that power grid systems face. Proper classification of different instability issues makes it much easier to analyze stability, including identifying the major causes of instability and coming up with solutions to

enhance stable operation [13]. The classification of power system stability carried out by the author in [15] is shown in Figure 2.1. This present study's focus is on rotor angle stability issues.

Figure 2.1: Classification of power system stability [15]

2.2.2 Rotor angle stability

Rotor angle stability refers to a synchronous machine's ability to maintain synchronism following a disturbance in an interconnected power grid system. It depends on each synchronous machine's ability to keep or restore equilibrium between the mechanical and electrical torque. The rotor angle stability problem involves studying electromechanical oscillations, a synchronous generator's characteristic in which the output power varies as the rotors oscillate at synchronous speed. Oscillations in synchronous machines are due to their dynamic nature. A synchronous generator may experience oscillations that appear as a series of sequential events due to any incident (little or large disruption) in the power grid system [4] this is shown in Figure 2.2. Under normal operating conditions, the synchronous generator rotor speed is maintained at synchronous speed by the balance between the mechanical and electrical torques. Any disturbance that affects

the equilibrium leads to rotor speed deviation from its synchronous speed. This phenomenon is best described in the swing equation as shown in the study [16].

Figure 2.2: Sequential events in electromechanical oscillations [4]

From Figure 2.2 it is shown that a change in the speed of the rotor leads to a change in the angle of the rotor. According to the power angle characteristics in the study [17], a change in the angle of the rotor also causes a change in generated power output. This sequential event is well known as the oscillations in the power grid system. Electromechanical oscillations are caused by imbalances between electrical and mechanical torques in synchronous generators.

In a wind-integrated single-machine connected to an infinite bus (SMIB) system, the wind turbine generator is connected to a single machine (the generator), which forms a grid of power lines. The transmission lines here are called "tie lines" because they connect two different systems. Electromechanical oscillations have a complicated nature. Understanding the various oscillation modes that are present in the system is crucial for fundamental analysis. The study in [18] generally classifies oscillation modes into three categories:

- i. **Local area modes:** This form of oscillation is between a synchronous generator and the overall power system components connected to the generator. Local area modes are small cycle oscillations with high frequencies in the range of 0.8 – 3.0 Hz [44].

- ii. Inter-area modes:** Inter-area modes of oscillation occur among generators in different regions connected via the transmission tie line. Inter-area modes are long-cycle oscillations with a low frequency of 0.2 – 0.7 Hz [45].
- iii. The global mode:** This is the oscillation of all generators in the system when the frequency is extremely low, between 0.01 Hz and 0.05 Hz.

These oscillations may continue for a long time, and it might be challenging to notice their presence, which could then destabilize the system [4]. Power grid system oscillations may affect the stability of the entire power system, and millions of people could experience power disruptions if the oscillations are not adequately damped.

2.2.3 Single machine infinite bus (SMIB)

The popular infinite bus is the terminal bus for a single machine that is connected to it. An infinite bus in power engineering language, is a bus with fixed voltage (both magnitude and angle) as well as frequency. In the infinite bus test system, injected power is absorbed in the connection point without significantly changing frequency or system voltage, simulating a strong grid connection [19]. The SMIB power test system consists of a single synchronous generator, hence the name single machine, as seen in Figure 2.3 shows a single-line schematic of the SMIB power test system. A stator with armature windings and a rotor (a cylindrical rotor or salient pole) with field windings make up a synchronous generator or machine. The d-axis and the q-axis are the two axes of symmetry, and the stator and rotor are separated from one another by a small air gap [30]. Time-varying fluxes between the armature and rotor circuits cause self- and mutual inductances to be produced as the rotor rotates with respect to the stator.

Figure 2.3: SMIB single-line diagram

2.2.4 Wind energy conversion system (WECS)

A wind energy conversion system (WECS) is used to generate wind energy. Electrically excited synchronous generators (EESG), squirrel-cage induction generators (SCIG), permanent magnet synchronous generators (PMSG), and doubly fed induction generators (DFIG) are the four types of generators utilized for variable wind speed conversion in wind energy [20].

Meanwhile, DFIG and PMSG have gotten more attention than EESG and SCIG due to their efficiency and high energy conversion rate, furthermore, they can be easily controlled. Due to the above reasons, this research makes use of the DFIG wind energy conversion system. Both DFIG and PMSG systems have almost the same amount of wind energy systems installed around the world [21]. The DFIG wind energy conversion system is made up of a gearbox, a rotor-side or machine-side converter (AC/DC), and a grid-side converter (DC/AC). The gearbox connects a wind turbine to the DFIG wind energy system and turns the mechanical energy from the turbine into electricity. [22], [23]. The DFIG system is shown in Figure 2.4. A wide range of variable speeds is possible with the three-phase winding rotor utilized in DFIG. Thus, active and reactive power rotor current flow in the converter is altered through variable speed control. However, it is important to perform routine maintenance on the brushes and multiple-stage gearboxes in the DFIG system to reduce the possibility of machine failure.

Figure 2.4 The DFIG system

2.2.5 Power system stabilizer (PSS) damping controller

Electromechanical oscillations occur without warning. The design of automated control and proper detection schemes like PSS damping controllers are necessary for the power grid system as there are used to damp these oscillations. PSS damping controller operates as a compensator for the phase lag error between the exciter input, electrical torque, and generator torque component of the rotor [6]. The installed PSS damping controller adds an extra input signal to the excitation system of the synchronous generator, the extra input signal acts as a synchronizing torque to the generator speed deviation and phase locks this signal to the generator speed deviation. Because of this, the stability of the system is improved, and the increasing oscillations are damped. Figure 2.5 shows the structure of a conventional PSS damping controller and it can be mathematically represented in Equation (2.1) as seen in the study [24].

$$G_i(s) = \frac{V_{PSSi}(s)}{\Delta\omega_i(s)} = K_{pssi} \frac{sT_W (1 + sT_{1i})(1 + sT_{3i})}{(1 + sT_W)(1 + sT_{2i})(1 + sT_{4i})} \quad (2.1)$$

The PSS damping controller consists of a control gain K_{pssi} , T_W which is a constant known as a washout filter, the phase compensators are two lead-lag blocks with parameters T_{1i} , T_{2i} , T_{3i} and T_{4i} and a limiter. V_{PSSi} is the PSS output signal which is the input to the excitation system of the generator. $\Delta\omega_i$ is PSS signal input which is the rotor speed deviation of the generator [25].

Figure 2.5: Structure of power system stabilizer [25]

2.2.6 Damping controller design and Performance

Damping of Electromechanical oscillation can be improved by providing a PSS damping controller mechanism to the excitation system of a synchronous generator [10]. An automatic voltage regulator (AVR) which controls the synchronous generator voltage by adjusting its field voltage tends to add negative damping to the synchronous generator, PSS damping controller is introduced to solve this problem and it is coupled in phase with the rotor of the synchronous generator to improve the dynamic performance of the system. Its objective is to control electromechanical oscillation in the system [26]. The inclusion of the PSS damping controller in the synchronous generator's operation results in a higher damping ratio, which in turn results in faster stabilization of oscillations [27]. The PSS damping controller connected to the synchronous generator's excitation system is shown in Figure 2.6.

Figure 2.6: A synchronous generator's excitation system with a PSS controller [12]

In the past, conventional PSS damping controllers with fixed parameters and simple structures were mostly utilized [28]. Modern power grid systems are dynamic and with renewable energy penetration it is quite complex. Presently, conventional PSS damping controller design for a specific operating condition may not cope with the dynamic nature of modern integrated power systems where operating conditions vary under wide operating ranges. Therefore, the PSS damping controller parameters need optimization to improve their efficiency in electromechanical oscillation damping. Due to its fast computational nature, meta-heuristic optimization techniques are deployed in PSS damping controller design, and meta-heuristics have the ability to provide optimal solutions [7], [29], [30].

2.2.7 Review of meta-heuristic optimization Techniques

Meta-heuristic algorithms provide the best solution to optimization problems by utilizing deep and global search procedures. The study in [31] provides a thorough review of the meta-heuristic algorithm and classified the algorithms into groups, one such group is the nature-inspired algorithms. Artificial eco-system optimization (AEO) is grouped under nature-inspired algorithms. The next section reviews the AEO algorithm and the reason it was adopted in this research.

2.2.7.1 Artificial eco-system optimization (AEO)

The study in [32] developed the artificial ecosystem which is a metaheuristic algorithm that is nature-inspired. AEO algorithm mimics Production, consumption, and decomposition operations which are the three unique behaviors of living organisms in an ecosystem. An ecosystem is defined as the complex of living organisms and their inter-relationships in their physical environment within a specific region of space. The two classes of ecosystems are abiotic (sunlight, water, and elements that are non-living) and biotic (all living elements). As per a

metaheuristic algorithm, the AEO search procedure is based on two important features, exploration, and exploitation. The production operation enhances the exploitation and exploration balance, the consumption operation improves the algorithm's exploration ability, and the decomposition process improves exploitation in the algorithm. In a population, the energy level of everyone is accessed based on the defined objective function, the objective function values are then used to sort individuals in the population in descending order. The individual from the population with the highest objective function value indicates the highest energy level which forms a minimization problem for optimization. Figure 2.7 depicts energy flow in an ecosystem.

Figure 2.7: Diagram representing energy flow in an ecosystem

AEO has been adopted in applications such as parameter estimation of solar photovoltaic models [33], proportional integral derivative (PID) controller design for buck converters [34], and economic emission dispatch [35]. But AEO hasn't been used in PSS damping controller design yet, so this study is the first to look at how well it works for optimal tuning of PSS damping controller in the power system.

2.2.8 Objective function for damping controller design

The electromechanical oscillation amplitude attenuation rate determines the damping ratio of a system, hence for quick attenuation of these oscillations the PSS damping controller parameters are obtained through optimization. Rotor speed deviation error results in electromechanical modes of oscillation, therefore to control and damp these electromechanical modes of oscillation is to reduce the error in the rotor speed deviation and in doing so, the damping ratio of the system is improved for quick oscillation attenuation. An eigenvalue objective function was defined to damp the electromechanical modes (EMs) and improve damping features in the system. The eigenvalue objective function is also able to place the conjugate eigenvalues (which describe oscillatory behavior in a linear system) on the left-hand side (LHS) of the complex S-plane which is the region of stability. The power system stabilizer (PSS) gain and lead-lag compensator parameters are obtained through this eigenvalue objective function, Equation (2.2) expresses this objective function which is adapted from the study in [19].

$$J = \max\{real(\lambda_i) | \lambda_i \in EMS\} + P_c \sum \{real(\lambda_j) | \lambda_j > 0\} \quad (1.2)$$

$$EMS = \left\{ \lambda_k \mid 0 < \frac{im(\lambda_k)}{2\pi} < 5 \right\}$$

Subject to $0.001 \leq K_{pssi} \leq 50$ and $0.001 \leq T_{1i} \leq 1$, $0.02 \leq T_{2i} \leq 1$, $0.001 \leq T_{3i} \leq 1$ and $0.02 \leq T_{4i} \leq 1$. From Equation (2.2) electromechanical modes (EMs) are obtained from the imaginary part of conjugate eigenvalues which represent the oscillation frequencies of the modes from 0 to 5 in this study, the first part of the defined objective function $\max\{real(\lambda_i) | \lambda_i \in EMS\}$ maximizes the damping of the identified electromechanical modes, the second part of the objective function $\sum\{real(\lambda_j) | \lambda_j > 0\}$ prevents the system from having unstable electromechanical modes (i.e. conjugate eigenvalues whose real part is above zero), P_c is a penalty constant that adjusts the

relative importance of the two parts of the objective function [19]. In this study, P_C is considered to be 50.

2.3 Review of Related Works

Particle swarm optimization, a metaheuristic algorithm was adopted in [36], the defined objective function was based on a critical damping index for the optimal design of the PSS damping controller in a single machine connected to an infinite bus power grid system. The proposed design was performed in Matlab/Simulink software. Results indicated improvement in terms of electromechanical damping ratio from 2.2% with No-PSS damping controller and 20.58% with fixed parameters or conventional PSS to 65.9% for particle swarm-optimized PSS. The settling time of the oscillation was reduced from 4 seconds with a conventional PSS damping controller to 2 seconds with particle swarm-optimized PSS. The proposed design was validated on the NEPLAN simulator tool. However, the particle swarm-optimized PSS was not validated against another meta-heuristic algorithm, to ascertain a robust design the proposed design should be compared with another meta-heuristic algorithm.

In the study [37] Dynamic behavior and analysis of a power grid system with a PSS damping controller design and excitation system stabilizer were carried out. To increase the damping characteristic and stability of a single machine connected to an infinite bus system, The synergistic control theory was adopted in the design of a PSS damping controller and an excitation system stabilizer. The synergetic controller does not need linearization of the power system model, hence it works on a non-linear system (thus the word synergy); here, a control variable (φ) is defined, and the synergetic control forces the system to act in ($\varphi = 0$). The control variable restricts system output and controls the system's settling time after a disturbance. The system (SMIB) with a synergetic power system stabilizer developed using Matlab software was evaluated

under three disturbance conditions (terminal voltage change in step, mechanical power input, and short circuit fault in the three phases). The proposed design showed a 44% reduction in settling time with synergetic PSS damping compared to a 20% reduction in settling time for the conventional PSS under a three-phase fault. However, the fault initiated at 0.1 seconds took quite a significant amount of time (past 4 seconds) for the speed deviation, electrical power, and rotor angle curves to settle as seen in the figures.

The slime mold algorithm was introduced in the PSS damping controller design for a single machine connected to an infinite bus system in the study [38]. The performance index of integral multiplied by time, multiplied by the absolute error was minimized. The proposed slime mold PSS damping controller design was compared to the fixed parameter or conventional PSS damping controller and the PSS damping controller designed using the grasshopper optimization algorithm. The slime mold-based PSS damping controller increased the damping ratio of the power grid system from 0.0095 with No-PSS damping controller to 0.0201 with a conventional PSS damping controller, 0.2678 with a grasshopper-optimized PSS damping controller, and 0.2850 with slime mold-based PSS damping controller. However, the author omitted the washout time constant (T_w) stage in PSS damping controller design stating that its addition plays no role in the damping controller design, but in study [39], the author argues that the washout time constant with the recommended value of 2-10 seconds helps to reduce noise, enables signals which help in oscillation damping to pass unchanged and also help in DC and low-frequency filtering. Hence it should not be omitted.

The atom search algorithm's limitation of imbalance between global and local search phases was improved in the study [40] by merging the atom search algorithm with the simulated annealing algorithm, and both formed an improved atom search algorithm. This proposed

improvement was implemented in the PSS damping controller design in a single machine connected to an infinite bus system. The obtained results were compared to other metaheuristic algorithms in symbiotic organisms and sine-cosine algorithms in the PSS damping controller's design. The damping ratio of the system was improved from 1.15% with No-PSS damping controller, 35.43% with the symbiotic organism search algorithm, 48.66% with the sine-cosine algorithm, and 53.45% with improved atom search optimization. However, the study itself noted that the power system is nonlinear and characterized by consistent variation over a wide operating range. The research did not consider varying the single machine connected to infinite bus operating conditions in terms of output power or voltage change to ascertain the performance of the atom search algorithm's PSS damping controller design.

Henry gas solubility optimization which is a metaheuristic algorithm was adopted in the study [6] for optimal power system stabilizer damping controller design in a single machine connected to an infinite bus system. The proposed algorithm for the PSS damping controller design was compared to the atom search optimization algorithm in the PSS damping controller design using the performance index of integral multiplied by time, multiplied by the absolute error. The power grid system damping ratio was improved from 0.0095 with No-PSS damping controller to 0.6528 with atom search optimized and 0.6521 with Henry gas solubility optimized PSS damping controller. But the study ignored T_2 and T_4 which are parameters of the PSS damping controller in its design. The review in [4] notes that a robust PSS damping controller is ensured only when all the parameters ($K_{pss}, T_1, T_2, T_3, T_4$) of the damping controllers are obtained through optimization.

An artificial gorilla troops optimization based on quantum theory was adopted in the study [41] to design robust power system stabilizers. Improving the gorilla troop optimization (GTO)

and adopting the ITAE objective function, the Monte Carlo method of randomization employing a quantum model was developed as a novel approach to tuning the conventional PSS (C-PSS), fractional order (FO) proportional integral derivative PSS (FOPID-PSS), tilt order derivative PSS (TID-PSS) and dual input PSS (DI-PSS) in a single machine connected to an infinite bus system in Matlab/Simulink software. For a 0.1 PU change in mechanical torque, TID-PSS had the least error value of 4.99×10^{-6} compared to DIPSS (2.72×10^{-3}) and FOPID-PSS (6.63×10^{-6}). However, the research did not consider varying the single machine connected to an infinite bus operating condition in terms of power output or voltage change to further access the robustness of the proposed design.

In the study [42], the arithmetic optimization algorithm was also merged with simulated annealing to improve its exploration and exploitation characteristics. An improved arithmetic optimization algorithm was proposed and implemented in the PSS damping controller design for a single machine connected to an infinite bus system. The obtained results were also verified by comparing them with other metaheuristic algorithms in symbiotic organism search algorithms and sine-cosine algorithms. The damping ratio of the system was improved from 1.15% with No-PSS damping controller, 35.43% with the symbiotic organism search algorithm, 48.66% with the sine-cosine algorithm, and 54.36% with modified arithmetic optimization. However, in presenting the integral time absolute error curve against time, which shows the path to optimization of the PSS damping controller, only the proposed improved arithmetic optimization algorithm curve was presented. The three optimization curves (improved arithmetic optimization, sine cosine algorithm, and symbiotic organisms search algorithms) needed to be presented and compared to show the different paths and points of convergence to the optimal solution for each algorithm.

The Sine cosine algorithm was adopted in [43] to design a PSS damping controller in a single machine connected to an infinite bus (SMIB) power grid system for rotor angle stability analysis. The sine cosine algorithm which is the proposed design for the PSS damping controller was validated by comparing the results from the performances of moth flame and evolutionary programming algorithms PSS damping controllers design under different loading conditions, the sine cosine algorithm had the shortest damping time (2.6 seconds) when compared to the evolutionary programming (before 6 seconds) and moth flame (2.7 seconds). However, the research did not consider the proposed Sine cosine algorithm PSS damping controller performance in a renewable integrated power grid system. In a renewable integrated power grid system, the major challenge is its intermittent nature, and thus uncertainty in operating conditions. Therefore, accessing the proposed sine cosine PSS damping controller design under uncertain operating conditions further ascertains its robustness.

Power system stabilizers (PSS) were modeled in a doubly fed induction generator (DFIG) wind renewable energy system in the study [44]. Two types of PSS damping controllers were proposed, active power system stabilizer and reactive power system stabilizer, and applied to a DFIG system with ratings of 575V, 1.5MW, and 50Hz using Matlab/Simulink software. The proposed PSSs damping controllers were used to enhance the power system dynamic performance by maintaining an almost unity power factor, faster oscillation damping, and better power control. Subjecting the test power system to fault (three-phase), simulation results showed a peak value of active power of 1.99 PU with the PSS damping controller and 4.021 PU without the PSS damping controller installed on the power grid system. The reactive power control in the system was also increased by 66.5% -1.67 PU peak value with the PSS damping controller and -2.78 PU without PSS on the system. However, in the design of the proposed PSS, the author did not specify whether

the parameters were obtained through trial and error (as in a conventional PSS) or optimization. The review in [4] notes that a robust damping controller is ensured only when all the parameters ($K_{pss}, T_1, T_2, T_3, T_4$) of the damping controllers are obtained through optimization.

In the study [45], a single machine connected to an infinite bus power grid system (SMIB), augmented by a DFIG wind energy system, was accessed by studying the dynamic operations of the system model at different wind speeds (12m/s, 9 m/s, and 7 m/s). The machine side or rotor side controller and grid side controllers, which are the two inbuilt controllers of the DFIG systems, were utilized as the damping controllers for electromechanical oscillation damping in the system. The gains of these controllers affect the power system stability of the test power system and were varied for the various operating conditions for improvement in overall system stability. At wind speed (12 m/s) and wind farm ratings of the DFIG system between 100 MW and 300 MW, it was observed that the damping ratios of the dominant eigenvalues with increased wind farm rating increases, and the dominant modes of the oscillation frequencies reduce relative to SMIB power test system only. The rotor-side and grid-side controllers stabilize these electromechanical modes. However, the PSS damping controller gains were selected based on trial and error technique for improving system stability. Table 2.1 summarizes the above-reviewed works of literature.

Table 2.1 Summary of Related Works.

Author's Name, Year, and Title of work	Work done	Result	Research gap
A.S. Alawad-Ali et al. (2019) Particle swarm optimization of PSS for Mitigation of SMIB Oscillations	The critical damping index was defined as the objective function in the optimal PSS damping controller design for a single machine connected to an infinite bus system	The results obtained show an improvement in damping ratio from 2.2% with No-PSS damping control and 20.58% with conventional PSS damping control to 65.9% for particle swarm-optimized PSS.	The particle swarm-optimized PSS was not validated against another meta-heuristic algorithm.

<p>A. Fattollahi et al. (2022) PSS and Excitation system stabilizers dynamic behavior, analysis, and simulation in a power system</p>	<p>Synergistic control theory was used to design a PSS damping controller and evaluated under three disturbance conditions.</p>	<p>Showed a 44% reduction in settling time with a synergetic PSS damping controller compared to a 20% reduction in settling time for the conventional PSS damping controller under a three-phase fault.</p>	<p>The fault initiated at 0.1 seconds took quite a significant amount of time (past 4 seconds) for the speed deviation, electrical power, and rotor angle curves to settle as seen in the figures.</p>
<p>S. Ekinci, (2020) Power system stabilizer application and design using Slime Mold algorithm</p>	<p>Adopting the ITAE performance index in SMIB with Matlab, The slime mold-designed PSS was compared to fixed parameter PSS and PSS design using grasshopper optimization.</p>	<p>The PSS design based on the slime mold algorithm increased the damping control by improving the damping ratio to 0.0201 with conventional PSS, 0.2678 with grasshopper-optimized PSS damping controller, and 0.2850 for slime mold-based PSS</p>	<p>The author omitted the washout time constant (T_w) stage in PSS damping controller design stating that ‘it plays no role in the PSS damping controller design.</p>
<p>D. Izci, (2022) Power system stabilizer based on a novel improved atom search optimization algorithm</p>	<p>This proposed improvement was implemented in the PSS design of the SMIB power system. The obtained results were compared to symbiotic search and sine-cosine algorithms for the PSS damping controller’s design</p>	<p>The damping ratio of the system was improved from 1.15% with No-PSS, 35.43% with the symbiotic organism search algorithm, 48.66% with the sine-cosine algorithm, and 53.45% with improved atom search optimization.</p>	<p>The research did not consider varying the single machine connected to infinite bus operating conditions to ascertain the PSS damping controller robustness.</p>
<p>D. Izci, (2022) Power system stabilizer based on a novel arithmetic optimization algorithm</p>	<p>An improved arithmetic optimization algorithm was proposed and implemented in the PSS design for SMIB. comparing them with the sine-cosine algorithm and symbiotic organism search algorithms.</p>	<p>The damping ratio of the system was improved from 1.15% with No-PSS, 35.43% with the symbiotic organism search algorithm, 48.66% with the sine-cosine algorithm, and 54.36% with modified arithmetic optimization.</p>	<p>The research did not compare the ITAE against the iterations curve for the proposed algorithm for PSS design with the evaluated algorithms for PSS design.</p>
<p>J. Bhukya et al. (2018) Doubly fed induction generator wind-based power system stabilizers</p>	<p>PSS damping controllers were proposed, active and reactive power stabilizers, and applied on a DFIG system with ratings 1.5MW, 50Hz, and 575V in</p>	<p>Under a three-phase fault, simulation results showed a peak value of active power of 1.99 PU with PSS, and 4.021 PU without the PSS damping controller on the system.</p>	<p>The PSS damping controller parameters were obtained through a trial-and-error method</p>

	Matlab/Simulink software	The reactive power control also increased by 66.5% with PSS damping control	
N. N. Shah et al. (2019) DFIG-based wind model utilization for robust damping control of power system oscillations in a single machine connected to an infinite bus	Under 7 m/s, 9 m/s, and 12 m/s wind speeds. The rotor side controller and grid side controllers which are the two inbuilt controllers of the DFIG systems were utilized as the damping controllers for electromechanical oscillation damping in the system	At 12 m/s wind speed, it was observed that the dominant eigenvalues increased as the wind farm rating increased, and the oscillation frequencies of dominant modes also decreased compared to SMIB only.	The PSS damping controller parameters were obtained through a trial-and-error method

2.3.1 RESEARCH GAP

The literature reviewed implies that to maintain a sustainable environment and meet the ever-growing demand for power supply, renewables like wind energy conversion system need to be introduced into the power grid system, however, the power grid system need to be stabilized before introducing renewables. This can be achieved through a Power system stabilizer (PSS) damping controller. PSS damping controller is coupled with the generator excitation systems to control electromechanical oscillations and provide stability. However, the PSS damping controller needs to be optimally designed. This research fills the gap by introducing a DFIG-wind renewable system to the grid to meet energy demand and environmental sustainability. Also introducing the artificial eco-system (AEO) optimization to optimally design the PSS damping controller.

2.4 Summary

This chapter has provided a good theoretical review and literature review of related works, which supports this research work. The theoretical background presented takes into account the analytical evaluations undertaken in the succeeding chapters.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter discusses all the methods with their mathematical formulations adopted in this research. The various mathematical formulations for the power system modeling were adopted from studies [17], [43], and [44]. The various power system models and data are adopted from [19], [46], [47].

3.2 MATERIAL

The simulations were carried out using Matlab/Simulink software 2020, on Hewlett-Packard Intel® CORE(TM)i3-10110U CPU@ 2.10GHz, 64-bit operating system in Windows 10 pro.

3.3 Step-by-step design of the blocks in this work process

The flowchart showing the procedure for the research is shown in Figure 3.1. Detailed Modeling of the test systems representing the power grid systems for rotor angle control and stability study is presented.

3.3.1 Power system model

The dynamic model of a power system is often described using differential algebraic equations (DAEs), a single machine connected to an infinite bus system (SMIB) relates to the conventional power grid system in this study while the doubly fed induction generator (DFIG) wind energy conversion system relates the renewable energy source.

3.3.1.1 Single machine Infinite bus system

In power engineering study the term single machine connected to an infinite bus system refers to an infinite bus which is a bus with fixed voltage and frequency, the fixed voltage is both in magnitude and angle.

Figure 3.1: Flow chart of the Step-by-step procedure for this research

This single machine connected to an infinite bus represents a strong grid connection, which means that at the connection point, which is the infinite bus, power is injected without a considerable change in the system frequency and voltage. The single machine or synchronous machine consists of the stationary part with armature windings known as the stator and the rotating part (can be salient pole or cylindrical rotor) with field windings called the rotor. In between these

two parts is the small air gap separating them, there also exist the d-axis and q-axis symmetry, which are the two axes that IEEE adopted for easy analysis and representation of the three-phase balanced voltage produced in the synchronous machine. As the rotating part, the rotor rotates relative to the stator circuits, inductances (self and mutual) are induced due to time-varying fluxes between the rotor and the stator armature circuits. In the analysis of synchronous machine and its modeling, these time-varying inductances complicate the process but dq transformations using the d-axis and q-axis symmetry are used to simplify the model. The solution loop of the SMIB generator power system is shown in Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2: Single machine infinite bus solution loop

The input to the SMIB generator system is bus voltage V_{DQ} obtained from the network block while current i_{DQ} is the model output which is injected into the network block. This generator system consists of two sides, the mechanical and electrical sides. The torque angle loop represents the mechanical side, while the synchronous machine block represents the electrical side, the governor and an excitation control block are also part of the system. The various blocks assembled to form the SMIB generator system are explained.

1. **Excitation system:** the excitation system by adjusting the field voltage of the generator helps to regulate the generator bus voltage. Equation (3.1) represents a simple excitation system, and the Simulink representation is shown in Figure 3.3

$$\frac{dE_{fd}}{dt} = \frac{1}{T_a} (K_a V_{ref} - K_a E_t - E_{fd}) \tag{2.1}$$

Figure 3.3 Simulink representation of excitation system, Equation (3.1)

2. **Torque Angle loop:** the torque angle loop expression in Equation (3.2) describes the rotor angle and rotor speed change when there is a mismatch between the torques in the synchronous generator mechanical system. The Simulink representation is shown in Figure 3.4

$$\frac{d\delta}{dt} = \omega_b (\omega_r - \omega_s) \tag{3.2}$$

$$\frac{d\omega_r}{dt} = \frac{1}{2H} (T_m - T_e - D(\omega_r - \omega_s))$$

Figure 3.4: Simulink representation of torque angle loop, Equation (3.2)

3. **Turbine-Governor:** the governor regulates the power system grid frequency, especially during changes in generation and load balancing, this is done by adjusting the generator input

torque. Equation (3.3) represents a simple governor while Figure 3.5 shows the Simulink representation.

$$\frac{dT_m}{dt} = \frac{1}{T_g} \left(T_{m2} - T_m - \frac{\omega_r - \omega_s}{R_{gov}} \right) \quad (3.3)$$

Figure 3.5: Simulink representation of turbine-governor control, Equation (3.3)

4. **Synchronous machine:** This is the SMIB generator's electrical side, the machine equations are divided into (a) electrical torque (T_e), (b) the stator current components in q and d axis, (c) q and d axis damper coil flux linkage due to transient EMF in the field (d) q and d axis damper coil flux linkage due to sub-transient EMF in the field
- a) Electrical torque: the electrical torque representation in Equation (3.4) can be used to calculate the value and the Simulink representation is shown in Figure 3.6.

$$T_e = \frac{x_d'' - x_{ls}}{x_d' - x_{ls}} E_q' I_q + \frac{x_d' - x_d''}{x_d' - x_{ls}} \psi_{1d} I_q + \frac{x_q'' - x_{ls}}{x_q' - x_{ls}} E_d' I_d - \frac{x_q' - x_q''}{x_q' - x_{ls}} \psi_{2q} I_d + (x_q'' - x_d'') I_d I_q \quad (3.4)$$

Figure 3.6: Simulink representation of electrical torque, Equation (3.4)

- iv. The stator current components in the q and d-axis are represented in q axis by Equation (3.5) as

$$I_q = \frac{R_s}{R_s^2 + x_d''^2} \left(E_q' \frac{x_d'' - x_{ls}}{x_d' - x_{ls}} + \psi_{1d} \frac{x_d' - x_d''}{x_d' - x_{ls}} - V_q \right) + \frac{x_d''}{R_s^2 + x_d''^2} \left(E_d' \frac{x_q'' - x_{ls}}{x_q' - x_{ls}} - \psi_{2q} \frac{x_q' - x_q''}{x_q' - x_{ls}} - V_d \right) \quad (3.5)$$

And in the d-axis by Equation (3.6) while the Simulink representations are shown in Figure 3.7.

$$I_d = \frac{R_s}{R_s^2 + x_d''^2} \left(E_d' \frac{x_q'' - x_{ls}}{x_q' - x_{ls}} - \psi_{2q} \frac{x_q' - x_q''}{x_q' - x_{ls}} - V_d \right) - \frac{x_d''}{R_s^2 + x_d''^2} \left(E_q' \frac{x_d'' - x_{ls}}{x_d' - x_{ls}} + \psi_{1d} \frac{x_d' - x_d''}{x_d' - x_{ls}} - V_q \right) \quad (3.6)$$

Figure 3.7: Simulink representation of stator components in q and d-axis, Equations (3.5) and

(3.6)

- v. d and q-axis damper coil flux linkage due to Transient EMF in the field, are represented in q axis by Equation (3.7) while the Simulink representation is shown in Figure 3.8.

$$\frac{dE_q'}{dt} = \frac{1}{T_{d0}'} \left[-E_q' + E_{fd} + (x_d - x_d') \left(I_d + \frac{x_d' - x_d''}{(x_d' - x_{ls})^2} \{ \psi_{1d} - E_q' - I_d(x_d' - x_{ls}) \} \right) \right] \quad (3.7)$$

Figure 3.8: Simulink representation of flux-linkage in q-axis due to transient EMF, Equation (3.8)

And in d axis by Equation (3.9) while the Simulink representation is shown in Figure 3.9

$$\frac{dE'_d}{dt} = \frac{1}{T'_{q0}} \left[-E'_d + (x_q - x'_q) \left(-I_q + \frac{x'_q - x''_q}{(x'_q - x_{ls})^2} \{ -\psi_{2q} - E'_d + I_q(x'_q - x_{ls}) \} \right) \right] \quad (3.9)$$

Figure 3.9: Simulink representation of flux-linkage in d-axis due to transient EMF, Equation (3.9)

- vi. d and q-axis flux linkage due to sub-transient EMF in the field is represented in the q-axis by Equation (3.10) while the Simulink representation is shown in Figure 3.10.

$$\frac{d\psi_{2q}}{dt} = \frac{1}{T''_{q0}} \left(-\psi_{2q} - E'_d + I_q(x'_q - x_{ls}) \right) \quad (3.10)$$

Figure 3.10: Simulink representation of flux-linkage in q-axis due to sub-transient EMF

And in the d-axis by Equation (3.11) while the Simulink representation is shown in Figure 3.11.

$$\frac{d\psi_{1d}}{dt} = \frac{1}{T''_{d0}} \left(-\psi_{1d} + E'_q + I_d(x'_d - x_{ls}) \right) \quad (3.11)$$

Figure 3.11: Simulink representation of flux-linkage in the d-axis due to sub-transient EMF

The subsystems developed so far from Figures 3.6 – 3.11, Equations (3.4 – 3.11) can be described as the synchronous generator electrical side. The subsystems are then grouped as in Figure 3.12.

Figure 3.12: Electrical side of the generator

The remaining part of the synchronous generator electrical side is the synchronous generator dq transformation frames, the dq -frame is for the generator while the DQ -frame for the network block. This conversion is necessary and has been derived and explained in the study [19] as reference frames. Voltage V_{DQ} in DQ -frame is fed to the generator, using Equation (3.12) the voltage is converted to dq -frame. The dq -frame current from the generator is converted back to DQ -frame for the network using Equation (3.13).

DQ to dq block: The generator voltage once converted is divided into the real (V_q) and imaginary (V_d) part of the Simulink representation is shown in Figure 3.13

$$V_q + jV_d = (V_Q + jV_D)e^{-j\delta} \quad (3.12)$$

Figure 3.13 Simulink representation for converting DQ to dq frame in Equation (3.12)

dq to DQ block: The reverse process is used here to convert the current back to DQ -frame for the network as shown in the Simulink representation in Figure 3.14

$$I_q + jI_d = (I_Q + jI_D)e^{-j\delta} \quad (3.13)$$

Figure 3.14 Simulink representation for converting dq to DQ frame in Equation (3.13)

Lastly, the Mathematical block for the DQ conversion provides the rotation terms for the phasors, here the angle (δ) is transformed into $e^{-j\delta}$ and $e^{j\delta}$ as seen in Figure 3.15.

Figure 3.15 Simulink representation for the mathematical block for exponentials

The electrical side of the generator in Figure 3.12 and the reference blocks explained above are now grouped into a larger system that represents the electrical machine equations. Figure 3.16 shows the Simulink representation.

Figure 3.16: Electrical machine equation block

The mechanical and electrical sides, including the excitation and the governor control system, complete the SMIB synchronous generator system. The solution loop of Figure 3.2 is now

represented in the Simulink model of Figure 3.17, with the PSS damping controller connected to the power system excitation block, the PSS damping controller design is explained in section 3.4.

Figure 3.17: Simulink representation of SMIB generator system

3.3.1.2 Network for the SMIB

The network is represented in Equation (3.14), changes in the generator current injection affect the network voltage and changes in the network voltage also affects the synchronous generator. The Simulink representation is shown in Figure 3.18.

Figure 3.18: Simulink representation of the network

The SMIB generator system in Figure 3.18 is converted into a generator block and attached to the network system in Figure 3.18 to complete the SMIB system, the complete system is shown in Figure 3.19.

Figure 3.19: The SMIB system in Simulink

3.3.1.3 System linearization

The power system is made up of various dynamic elements and is modeled using mathematical differential algebraic equations (DAEs) as shown in the power test systems of SMIB and DFIG models. This power system DAEs are solved using ordinary differential equations (ODEs) solver in Matlab/Simulink IDE. However, PSS damping controller design is based on the control theory of a linear system, hence the non-linear power system model is converted to a linear system/linearized using the *'linmod'* command in the Matlab command window. The linearized model is extracted from the non-linear power system model before the PSS damping controller can be designed. This section explains basic expressions for the linearization approach for differential equations (DE). The operations of a now linear power system can be explained by a DAE in first-order in the following form as in Equation (3.15):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dy}{dx} &= f(x, z, u) \\ 0 &= g(x, z, u) \\ y &= h(x, z, u) \end{aligned} \tag{3.15}$$

Where from equation (3.15), f is the nonlinear DEs function that denotes the system controller dynamics, x is the system vector which involves generator angle, speed, flux, transient voltage, automated voltage regulator (AVR) output, excitation system, etc., z denotes the algebraic variables which include the system voltage angle and size, the stator currents, etc., u is the

reference vector which involves excitation control reference voltage, mechanical input, and other input variables and y denotes the output vector with signals such as generator speed, line power, system voltage size. By linearizing Equations around an operating point, Equation (3.15) initial equilibrium is achieved as shown in Equations (3.16-3.18).

$$\frac{d\Delta x}{dt} = \frac{\partial f}{\partial x} \Delta x + \frac{\partial f}{\partial z} \Delta z + \frac{\partial f}{\partial u} \Delta u \quad (3.16)$$

$$\Delta y = \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} \Delta x + \frac{\partial h}{\partial z} \Delta z + \frac{\partial h}{\partial u} \Delta u \quad (3.17)$$

$$0 = \frac{\partial g}{\partial x} \Delta x + \frac{\partial g}{\partial z} \Delta z + \frac{\partial g}{\partial z} \Delta z + \frac{\partial g}{\partial u} \Delta u \quad (3.18)$$

Δz can be removed from the above equations and thus the state equation of the power system can be represented in Equation (3.19) below:

$$\frac{d\Delta x}{dt} = A\Delta x + B\Delta u \quad (3.19)$$

$$\Delta y = C\Delta x + D\Delta u$$

Where x = State vector, u = Input vector, y = Output vector, A = State matrix, B = Input matrix, C = Output matrix, and D = Feed forward matrix.

3.3.1.4 Objective Function Formulation

Rotor speed deviation error results in electromechanical modes of oscillation, to enhance the damping characteristics of the power system electromechanical modes (EMs), is to reduce the error in the rotor speed deviation, through which the damping ratio is maximized for faster oscillation attenuation. The eigenvalue objective function is also able to place the conjugate eigenvalues (which describe oscillatory behavior in a linear system) on the left-hand side (LHS) of the complex S-plane which is the region of stability. The power system stabilizer (PSS) gain

and lead-lag compensator parameters are obtained through this eigenvalue objective function, Equation (3.20) expresses this objective function.

$$J = \max\{real(\lambda_i) | \lambda_i \in EMS\} + P_C \sum \{real(\lambda_j) | \lambda_j > 0\} \quad (3.20)$$

$$EMS = \left\{ \lambda_k \mid 0 < \frac{im(\lambda_k)}{2\pi} < 5 \right\}$$

Subject to $0.001 \leq K_{pssi} \leq 50$ and $0.001 \leq T_{1i} \leq 1$, $0.02 \leq T_{2i} \leq 1$, $0.001 \leq T_{3i} \leq 1$ and $0.02 \leq T_{4i} \leq 1$. From Equation (3.20) electromechanical modes (EMs) are obtained from the imaginary part of conjugate eigenvalues which represent the oscillation frequencies of the modes from 0 to 5 in this study, the first part of the defined objective function $\max\{real(\lambda_i) | \lambda_i \in EMS\}$ maximizes the damping of the identified electromechanical modes, the second part of the objective function $\sum\{real(\lambda_j) | \lambda_j > 0\}$ prevents the system from having unstable electromechanical modes (i.e. conjugate eigenvalues whose real part is above zero), P_C is a penalty constant that adjusts the relative importance of the two parts of the objective function [50]. In this study, P_C is considered to be 50. The AEO algorithm proposed for PSS design computes the defined optimization problem using the objective function and constraints to obtain optimal values.

3.3.1.5 PSS DAMPING CONTROLLER DESIGN

This research makes use of the lead-lag PSS damping controller connected to the IEEE-ST1 excitation system for analysis [50], the transfer function equation of the PSS damping controller is expressed in Equation (3.21), as adopted from the study [51].

$$G_i(s) = \frac{V_{PSSi}(s)}{\Delta w_i(s)} = K_{pssi} \frac{T_w s (1 + sT_{1i}) (1 + sT_{3i})}{(1 + sT_w) (1 + sT_{2i}) (1 + sT_{4i})} \quad (3.21)$$

Figure 3.20: Simulink representation of the PSS

The PSS damping controller output signal at the i th synchronous machine is V_{PSSi} , T_w is known as the washout time constant whose value is 10 in this study, the i th synchronous machine rotor speed deviation signal is Δw_i . Optimal parameter of the power system stabilizer damping controller gain K_{pssi} and parameters T_{1i} , T_{2i} , T_{3i} , and T_{4i} , are obtained through optimization.

3.3.1.6 Artificial Eco-System Optimization (AEO)

In Chapter 2, the basic principles of the AEO algorithm were explained. Here the mathematical modeling of the AEO algorithm for PSS damping controller design is explained. The three behavioral processes are production (producer), consumption (consumers in omnivore, carnivore, and herbivore), and decomposition (decomposer). It is assumed that in the ecosystem there exists just one producer as an individual, also just one decomposer exists as an individual in a population as seen in Figure 3.21. The rest of the population in the ecosystem are consumers with each having the same probability of been chosen.

Figure 3.21: An ecosystem in AEO

The producer from Figure 3.21 is the worst individual (x_1), because it is assumed to have the highest objective function value (high energy), and the best individual is the decomposer (x_n), it is assumed to have the lowest objective function value (least energy). The others are consumers, it

is assumed (x_2 and x_3) are herbivores (animals feeding on plants only), (x_5 and x_6) are omnivores (animals feeding on both plants and animals) while (x_4 and x_7) are carnivores (animals feeding on animals only).

i. Production process: In a defined population, the producer is assumed as the worst individual, its position is updated through the upper and lower boundaries in the search space and through the decomposer which in this scenario is assumed the best individual. The updated producer in turn guides the consumers which include (omnivores, carnivores, and herbivores) in the search for optimal solutions. In AEO, a production operator (x_n) is defined which provides a new search entity randomly in the AEO algorithm. This new search entity displaces the former. The latter is now assumed as the best entity, while the randomly produced search space is known (x_{rand}). The production operator is used mathematically described in Equations (3.22 – 3.24) as follows.

$$x_1(t + 1) = (1 - a)x_n(t) + ax_{rand}(t) \quad (3.22)$$

$$a = \left(1 - \frac{t}{maxit}\right)r_1 \quad (3.23)$$

$$x_{rand} = r \cdot (U_{PSS}^{max} - L_{PSS}^{min}) + L_{PSS}^{min} \quad (3.24)$$

Where the population size is represented by n , $maxit$ is the stop criteria which is the maximum number of iterations to be performed, U_{PSS}^{max} and L_{PSS}^{min} are the upper and lower boundaries of the PSS respectively, r_1 and r are randomly generated values and vectors respectively within the range of $[0,1]$, the weight coefficient a is used to shift an individual towards the position of the best individual with increased iteration. x_{rand} as explained is an individual position randomly produced in search space. $x_1(t + 1)$ is the producer itself which during early iterations may guide individuals to explore the search space while in later iterations, it may guide the other individuals to exploit the search space around the best individual (x_n).

ii. Consumption process

The consumption process takes place after production by the consumers. In order to obtain food that gives energy, consumers may either feed on each other depending on one's energy level and the producer as well. The levy flight operation is introduced to improve the optimization process, its mathematical operation mimics the food search in animals. The levy flight operation is a randomization process that can help to explore efficiently the defined search space. It helps to guide the exploration process with the promise of finding the optimum solution. Though two drawbacks exist in this operation when tuning a complex system and a system with several parameters, however, the levy flight includes a consumption factor C which is a simple parameter to support this randomization and overcome the drawbacks. This is shown in Equations (3.25-3.26).

$$C = \frac{1}{2} \frac{v_1}{|v_2|} \quad (3.25)$$

$$v_1 \in N(0,1), \quad v_2 \in N(0,1) \quad (3.26)$$

$N(0,1)$ is known as the normal distribution with a standard deviation value of 1 and a mean value of 0. The defined consumption factor is important because it helps the consumers hunt for food. The three consumers use unique consumption strategies.

A herbivore can only eat the producer when randomly chosen as a consumer, its operation is mathematically represented as shown in Equation (3.27).

$$x_i(t+1) = x_i(t) + C \cdot (x_i(t) - x_1(t)), \quad i \in [2, \dots, n] \quad (3.27)$$

However, a carnivore can eat only a consumer with a higher energy level when randomly chosen as the consumer, its operation is mathematically represented as shown in Equations (3.28-3.29) as follows.

$$x_i(t + 1) = x_i(t) + C. (x_i(t) - x_j(t)) \quad i \in [3, \dots, n] \quad (3.28)$$

$$j = randi([2i - 1]) \quad (3.29)$$

Also, an omnivore can feed on both a consumer with a higher energy level and the producer as well, when chosen randomly as the consumer, Its operation is mathematically modeled in Equations (3.30-3.31) as follows.

$$x_i(t + 1) = x_i(t) + C. (r_2. (x_i(t) - x_1(t)) + (1 - r_2) (x_i(t) - x_j(t)) \quad i = 3, \dots, n \quad (3.30)$$

$$j = randi([2i - 1]) \quad (3.31)$$

Where r_2 with a range of $[0, 1]$ is a generated random number.

iii. Decomposition process

The decomposition process is the last but it is a very essential one, the decomposer breaks down the chemical nutrients of each individual after death. It also provides the producer with the required nutrient for growth in a recycling process. A decomposition factor D with weight coefficients e and h are introduced in the mathematical expressions of the decomposition process shown in Equations (3.32-3.33),

$$x_i(t + 1) = x_n(t) + D. (e. x_n(t) - h. x_i(t)), \quad i = 1, \dots, n \quad (3.32)$$

$$D = 3u, \quad u \in N(0,1) \quad (3.33)$$

The x_n value is used to update the position of the i th individual in a population by the decomposer via these parameters D , e , and h . It also improves the exploitation process by allowing the next position of each individual to circle the decomposer which is assumed the best individual.

The steps of the AEO algorithm for optimal PSS tuning are as follows.

1. Initialize a search space randomly in an ecosystem. Each obtained solution is defined by a vector, x , $x = [K_{PSS}, T_1, T_2, T_3, T_4]$ in the PSS controller.
2. Calculate each eco-system energy level via the objective function Equation (3.20) and update the best solution.
3. Production process: using Equation (3.22), update the position for an individual x_1 .
4. Consumption process: each consumer has the same probability of selection, hence for individuals $x_2 \dots x_n$ its position is updated using Equation (3.27) if the selected individuals are herbivores if the selected individual are carnivores, their position is updated using Equation (3.28), and using if they are omnivores Equation (3.30) is deployed.
5. Calculate each eco-system energy level via Equation (3.20) and update the result as the best solution.
6. Decomposition process: Each position is updated using Equation (3.32).
7. Calculate each eco-system energy level via the objective function Equation (3.20) and update the best solution.
8. Repeat the steps carried out from 3-7 until the maximum number of iterations.
9. A population with a higher flow of energy is chosen as the best or optimal solution.

The flowchart of these steps is shown in Figure 3.22.

Figure 3.22: Flow chart of the Artificial ecosystem optimization process for PSS design

In this research, meta-heuristic algorithms in the genetic algorithm (GA) and particle swarm optimization (PSO) were adopted to validate the proposed artificial ecosystem optimization (AEO) in PSS design. This was done by comparing their performances based on obtained results in chapter four. As the study in [52] notes, of all the meta-heuristic algorithms adopted in PSS damping controller design, GA and PSO are the most widely utilized. The procedure for GA and PSO is explained,

3.3.1.7 Genetic Algorithm: The basic concept and mathematical expressions of GA can be seen in the study [53], the steps for GA application to PSS design are explained below;

The steps of the GA algorithm for optimal PSS tuning are as follows.

1. Initialize population, the vector $x = [K_{PSS}, T_1, T_2, T_3, T_4]$ is the PSS controller parameters.
2. Select parents and perform crossover.
3. Perform mutation operation (mutate off-springs from parents).
4. Merge main population and off-springs.
5. Evaluate, sort, and select new population
6. Go to step 2, if maximum iteration is not reached, and repeat the evolution loop otherwise end.

The flowchart of these steps is shown in Figure 3.23.

Figure 3.23: Flow chart of the Genetic algorithm process for PSS design

3.3.1.8 Particle swarm optimization: The mathematical formulation and explanation of PSO can be seen in the study [54], the steps for PSO application to PSS design are explained below;

The steps of the PSO algorithm for optimal PSS tuning are as follows.

1. Initialize population size, the vector $x = [K_{PSS}, T_1, T_2, T_3, T_4]$ is the PSS controller parameters.
2. Specify parameters of PSO which include w which is the inertia coefficient, c_1 the personal acceleration coefficient and c_2 the social acceleration coefficient.
3. Initialize velocity and particle position, evaluate the objective function, and global best.
4. Iteration loop, update position, velocity, update global best and evaluate the objective function
5. Go to step 3, if maximum iteration is not reached otherwise end.

The flowchart of these steps is shown in Figure 3.24.

Figure 3.24: Flow chart of the Particle swarm optimization process for PSS design

3.3.1.9 Doubly Fed Induction Generator Model (DFIG)

The power system model used to relate the renewable energy source in this study is the doubly fed induction generator model which is divided into seven for modeling purposes, there include the Turbine, the generator itself, the LCL filter, back-to-back capacitor (B2BC), the rotor/machine side converter, Network, and the grid side converter.

1. Turbine: Wind speed is fed to the wind turbine and electrical torque inputs; in turn, it provides generator speed as output. The turbine relates wind speed to the induction generator rotor speed

It is divided into two subsystems.

- i. An aerodynamic model: it converts the wind speed in the turbine to mechanical output.

The mechanical output of the turbine can be represented in Equation (3.34).

$$P_t = 0.5\rho\pi R^2 C_p(\beta, \lambda) V_w^3 \quad (3.34)$$

Where the air density is given as ρ , the wind speed is given by V_w , R is the turbine blade length, $C_p(\beta, \lambda)$ represent the blade's power coefficient which is part of wind power that can be extracted by the turbine, and it depends on the functions β, λ . In a practical setup, the performance curve of the turbine is specified through the tested field data. However, for simulation purpose, Equations representing numerical approximations adopted from the study [48] is given in Equation (3.35), and the Simulink representation is shown in Figure 3.25.

$$C_p(\beta, \lambda) = 0.5176 \left(\frac{116}{\lambda + 0.08\beta} - \frac{4.06}{1 + \beta^3} - 0.4\beta - 5 \right) e^{\left(\frac{-21}{\lambda + 0.08\beta} + \frac{0.735}{1 + \beta^3} \right)} + 0.0068\lambda \quad (3.35)$$

Figure 3.25: Simulink representation of turbine performance coefficient equation

Where the blade pitch angle is β , λ is the tip turbine speed ratio and is thus calculated using Equation (3.36). The combination of Equations (3.34-3.36) makes up the aerodynamic model shown in Figure 3.26.

$$\lambda = \frac{w_t R}{V_w} = \frac{w_t p u w_{trated} R}{V_w} \quad (3.36)$$

Where w_{trated} is the turbine-rated speed, w_t is the turbine speed. V_w or S_w is the wind speed.

Figure 3.26: Simulink representation of the turbine aerodynamic model

- ii. The drive train model uses the mechanical power output to drive the induction generator. The drive train model uses two masses attached to the shaft adopted from the study [49] shown in Equation (3.37), while the Simulink representation is shown in Figure 3.27.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{d}{dt}w_g &= \frac{1}{2H_g}(T_s - T_g) \\
 T_s &= K_{tg}\theta_{tg} + C_{tg}\frac{d}{dt}\theta_{tg} \\
 \frac{d}{dt}\theta_{tg} &= w_e B(w_t - w_s) \\
 \frac{d}{dt}w_t &= \frac{1}{2H_t}(T_t - T_s)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3.37}$$

Figure 3.27: Simulink representation of the drive train model of the wind turbine

From Equation (3.37), subscripts $g, s,$ and t refer to the generator, shaft, and turbine. The torque is given as T , w is the generator rotor speed, θ_{tg} is the generator shaft angle twist, H is the generator inertia, K_{tg} is shaft stiffness of the drive train, C_{tg} is the coefficient damping of the drive train and $w_e B$ is the electrical base speed.

- Generator: the generator takes the rotor speed from the generator (w_g), the bus voltage of the generator (V_g) from the network model as inputs and in turn, generate the output current (i_g) and electrical torque (T_g). The name DFIG means it has two feeds the stationary part stator

and the rotating part rotor. The stator windings are arranged such that the output stator currents produce a magnetic field that is rotating at angular speed in the air gap. The stator currents (i_{sd}, i_{sq}) in dq reference (same as the SMIB conversion process) produced in the generator can be represented by Equations (3.38-3.39) while the Simulink diagram is shown in Figure 3.28.

$$\frac{L'_s}{\omega_{el}B} \frac{d}{dt} i_{sd} = -\omega_s L'_s i_{sq} - R_1 i_{sd} + \frac{e'_{sq}}{\omega_s T_r} + \frac{\omega_g e'_{sd}}{\omega_s} + v_{sd} + K_{mrr} v_{rd} \quad (3.38)$$

$$\frac{L'_s}{\omega_{el}B} \frac{d}{dt} i_{sq} = -R_1 i_{sq} + \omega_s L'_s i_{sd} + \frac{\omega_g e'_{sq}}{\omega_s} - \frac{e'_{sd}}{\omega_s T_r} - v_{sq} + K_{mrr} v_{rq} \quad (3.39)$$

Figure 3.28: Simulink representation of the generator stator currents

Voltages behind transient impedances (e'_{sq}, e'_{sd}) are represented in Equations (3.40-3.41) and the Simulink representation is shown in Figure 3.29.

$$\frac{1}{\omega_s \omega_{el}B} \frac{d}{dt} e'_{sd} = -R_2 i_{sq} - \left(1 - \frac{\omega_g}{\omega_s}\right) e'_{sq} - \frac{e'_{sd}}{\omega_s T_r} + K_{mrr} v_{rq} \quad (3.40)$$

$$\frac{1}{\omega_s \omega_{el}B} \frac{d}{dt} e'_{sq} = R_2 i_{sd} - \frac{e'_{sd}}{\omega_s T_r} + \left(1 - \frac{\omega_g}{\omega_s}\right) e'_{sd} - K_{mrr} v_{rd} \quad (3.41)$$

Figure 3.29: Simulink representation of the Voltages behind transient impedances

Rotor currents i_{rq} and i_{rd} are given by Equation (3.42) and shown in Figure 3.29

$$\begin{aligned}
 i_{rq} &= -\left(\frac{e'_{sd}}{X_m}\right) - K_{mrr}i_{sq} \\
 i_{rd} &= \left(\frac{e'_{sq}}{X_m}\right) - K_{mrr}i_{sd}
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.42}$$

Rotor active power P_r , stator reactive power Q_s and electrical torque T_g are given as Equations

(3.43-3.45) the Simulink representation is in Figure 3.30

$$P_r = V_{rq}i_{rq} + V_{rd}i_{rd} \tag{3.43}$$

$$Q_s = -V_{sq}i_{sd} + V_{sd}i_{sq} \tag{3.44}$$

$$T_g = L_m(i_{sq}i_{rd} - i_{sd}i_{rq}) \tag{3.45}$$

Figure 3.30: Simulink block for Rotor active power, stator reactive power, and electrical torque

The complete generator block developed so far is shown in Figure 3.31.

Figure 3.31: Simulink representation of the inside view of the generator block

3. Filter: To complete the DFIG, the power grid system is linked to the rotor winding, the rotor winding consists of a back-to-back capacitor, filter, and converters. An inductor-capacitor-inductor (LCL) type of filter is used in this study. It is made of two inductors (L_i, L_g), a damping resistor (R_c) and a capacitor (C_f). The LCL model takes inverter voltage (v_{iq}, v_{id}) and stator voltage (v_{sq}, v_{sd}) as inputs and provides the current injected into the grid through the filter

(i_{gq}, i_{gd}) as outputs. The filter Equations are shown from (3.46 – 3.47) and the Simulink blocks are from Figure 3.32 – Figure 3.34 respectively.

$$\frac{L_i}{w_b} \frac{d}{dt} ii_q = v_{iq} - v_{cq} - (R_i + R_c)ii_q + w_g L_i ii_d + R_c i_{gq} \quad (3.46)$$

$$\frac{L_i}{w_b} \frac{d}{dt} ii_d = v_{id} - v_{cd} - (R_i + R_c)ii_d - w_g L_i ii_q + R_c i_{gd} \quad (3.47)$$

Figure 3.32: Simulink representation of the inverter side of the filter

$$\frac{L_g}{w_b} \frac{d}{dt} i_{gq} = v_{cq} - v_{sq} - (R_g + R_c)i_{gq} + w L_g i_{gd} + R_c ii_q \quad (3.48)$$

$$\frac{L_g}{w_b} \frac{d}{dt} i_{gd} = v_{cd} - v_{sd} - (R_g + R_c)i_{gd} - w L_g i_{gq} + R_c ii_d \quad (3.49)$$

Figure 3.33: Simulink representation of the grid side of the filter

$$\frac{C_f}{w_b} \frac{d}{dt} v_{cq} = i_{iq} - i_{gq} - w C_f v_{cd} \quad (3.50)$$

$$\frac{C_f}{w_b} \frac{d}{dt} v_{cd} = i_{id} - i_{gd} + w C_f v_{cq} \quad (3.51)$$

Figure 3.34: Simulink representation of the capacitor block inside the filter

Measure P and measure Q represent the converter terminal active power output and output reactive power at the filter terminal. It is modeled as seen in Equations (3.52 and 3.53) while the Simulink blocks are shown in Figure 3.35:

$$P_{gsc} = v_{iq}i_{iq} + v_{id}i_{id} \quad (3.52)$$

$$Q_{gsc} = -v_{sq}i_{gd} + v_{sd}i_{gq} \quad (3.53)$$

Figure 3.35: Simulink representation of the filter terminal active and reactive power output

Figure 3.36 shows the complete filter block developed so far

Figure 3.36: Simulink representation of the inside view of the filter block

4. Back-to-back Capacitor (B2BC): This B2BC connects the rotor windings to the power grid system through the LCL filter. The capacitor has a dc link, the capacitor voltage can be represented by Equation (3.54)

$$\frac{1}{C_{dc}} P V_{dc} = \frac{1}{V_{dc}} (P_{msc} - P_{gsc}) \quad (3.54)$$

Where P_{msc} is the machine side converter active power, P_{gsc} is the grid-side converter active power. The capacitor voltage V_{dc} , the capacitance is C_{dc} . Figure 3.37 shows the Simulink representation.

Figure 3.37: Simulink representation of the back-to-back capacitor of the DFIG system

The systems (blocks) developed so far either represent the mechanical or electrical subsystems of the DFIG power test system, there are quite different from the controllers or converters in the sense that the converters are power electronics converters that contain microcontrollers which are run by some software codes.

5. Machine side converter: The converter or controller model receives voltages, generator rotor speed and current in the form of electrical signals and produces corresponding switching signals for the converter. The vector control method through which independent control of active and reactive power, torque, and voltage control is achieved is adopted in this study. However, this vector control is possible only when one of the dq axes is aligned to the stator voltage. The DFIG power test system developed so far has the q -axis aligned to the infinite bus voltage. The measurements of the voltage and current must be aligned to a new reference frame which is inside the power test system controllers. The controllers adopted in this study have a simple model of two cascaded proportional-integral (PI), The two cascaded PI control loops are.

- i. The inner loops (MSC_IL1, MSC_IL2) are fast current controllers.
- ii. The outer loops (MSC_OL1, MSC_OL2) are slower torque or reactive power controllers.

The block diagram of the machine-side converter is shown below in Figure 3.38

Figure 3.38: Machine side converter (MSC) block diagram

The machine side converter (MSC) in Figure 3.38 is represented in Simulink in Figure 3.39, as explained in the machine side converter (MSC), the voltages (V'_{rq}, V'_{rd}) and currents (i'_{rq}, i'_{rd}) are converted to a new dq reference frame where the stator voltage is aligned to the q-axis.

Figure 3.39: Simulink representation of the machine-side converter model

To convert the two reference frames the phasor to angle θ is rotated, this angle is the stator voltage angle (DFIG bus voltage) The dq to dq' and dq' to dq blocks at both ends of Figure 3.39 represents the two reference frames conversion. Figure 3.40 shows the conversion from (i_{rd}, i_{rq})

to (i'_{rd}, i'_{rq}) and Figure 3.42 shows the conversion from (v'_{rd}, v'_{rq}) to (v_{rd}, v_{rq}) while Figure 3.41 shows the PI controllers of the machine-side converter.

Figure 3.40: Simulink representation of the conversion from dq to dq'

Figure 3.41: Simulink representation of the PI controllers in the machine-side controller

Figure 3.42: Simulink representation of the conversion from dq' to dq

6. Grid side converter: Like the machine side converter/controller, it also has two cascaded proportional-integral (PI) controllers regulating the voltage capacitor and reactive power flow from the grid side controller at the wind turbine generator bus. Rotor power is transferred to the grid ($P_r = P_{gsc}$), by regulating the capacitor voltage reference value. The block diagram representation of the grid-side converter controller is shown below in Figure 3.43.

Figure 3.43: Block diagram of grid side converter (GSC)

In the above block diagram which is represented in Simulink in Figure 3.44 as with the MSC, the voltages (VQ', VD') and currents (IQ', ID') are in a new reference frame.

Figure 3.44: Simulink representation of the grid side converter model

The DQ to DQ' and DQ' to DQ blocks at both ends of Figure 3.44 represents conversion between the two reference frames. Figure 3.47 shows the conversion from (iQ, iD) to (iQ', iD') and while Figure 3.46 shows the PI controllers of the DFIG power test system grid-side converter.

Figure 3.45: Simulink representation of the conversion from DQ to DQ'

Figure 3.46: Simulink representation of the PI controllers in the grid-side controller

Figure 3.47: Simulink representation of the conversion from DQ' to DQ

3.3.1.10 NETWORK OF THE DFIG

The network block is shown in Figure 3.48, the stator currents (i_{sq}, i_{sd}) and the currents injected into the grid through the filter (i_{gq}, i_{gd}) are the outputs of the DFIG system while the stator voltages (V_{sd}, V_{sq}) are the inputs to the DFIG system from the network.

Figure 3.48: Simulink representation of the DFIG network

The complete DFIG system is shown in Figure 3.49, with the seven DFIG power system blocks.

Figure 3.49: Simulink representation of the whole DFIG system

3.3.1.11 NETWORK OF SMIB AND DFIG

Assuming V_b , Z_{net} and I_b be vector (5×1) of bus voltages as seen in Chapter Four (Figure 4.10), impedance matrix (5×5), and vector (5×1) of the bus current injection. V_b can be represented in Equation (3.55) as

$$V_b = Z_{net} I_b \quad (3.55)$$

The current injection at bus 2 is from the SMIB power test system while bus 4 is from DFIG.

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_1 \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ V_4 \\ V_5 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Z_{1,1} & \dots & Z_{1,4} & Z_{1,5} \\ \cdot & \dots & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \dots & \cdot & \cdot \\ Z_{4,1} & \dots & Z_{4,4} & Z_{4,5} \\ Z_{5,1} & \dots & Z_{5,4} & Z_{5,5} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I_1 \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ I_4 \\ I_5 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.56)$$

There are no current injections at 1 and 3. Bus 5 is the infinite bus, the current injection (I_5) at bus 5 is unknown, but the voltage is known. Hence Equation (3.56) can be rewritten as in Equation (3.57):

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_b \\ V_5 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Z_A & Z_B \\ Z_C & Z_D \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I_B \\ I_5 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.57)$$

From Equation (3.57), Equation (3.58) is deduced

$$I_5 = Z_D^{-1}(V_5 - Z_C I_b) \quad (3.58)$$

The voltage is given in Equation (3.59) while the Simulink representation is shown in Figure 3.50

$$V_b = (Z_A - Z_B Z_D^{-1} Z_C) I_b + Z_B Z_D^{-1} V_5 \quad (3.59)$$

Figure 3.50: Simulink representation of the SMIB and DFIG network

3.3.1.12 INTEGRATED SMIB AND DFIG INTO THE NETWORK

The SMIB power test system in Figure 3.17 and the DFIG power test system in Figure 3.49 is integrated into one system to the network of the power system of Figure 3.50 to complete the integrated power grid system shown in Figure 3.51, the bus selector block (Smachs, Dmachs) specifies the bus number.

Figure 3.51: Simulink representation of the SMIB and DFIG system connected to the network

3.4 Conclusion

This chapter has provided the mathematical formulation of the power test systems. PSS design using AEO, PSO, and GA has also been presented with their respective flowcharts. The next chapter will present various simulation results.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS PRESENTATION AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Introduction

This chapter provides the results obtained from simulations which are through the implementation of the methodology on Matlab/Simulink software. Most importantly, the simulation of the AEO algorithm and its performance evaluation on the test systems.

4.2 SMIB TEST SYSTEM

The SMIB system modeled in chapter three is now used for numerical simulations, Figure 4.1 shows the SMIB single-line diagram. The bus data and line data adopted from [19] are shown in Tables 4.1 and 4.2.

Figure 4.1: SMIB single-line diagram

Tables 4.1. SMIB Bus data

Bus NO.,	Voltage	Angle	Pg	Qg	PL	QL	GL	BL	Bus type
1	1.026	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1
2	1.025	0.00	1.63	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	2

Table 4.2. SMIB Line data

From Bus No	To Bus No	R	X	B	Tap	Ratio
01	02	0	0.2625	0.00	1.0	0.0

The script “SMIB_run.m” in the appendix uses the functions “form_Ymatrix” and “power_flow” which take bus and line data from Tables 4.1 and 4.2 and outputs the Y admittance matrix result and also the bus and line flow solution shown below in Figure 4.2

```

Y =
    0.0000 - 3.8095i    0.0000 + 3.8095i
    0.0000 + 3.8095i    0.0000 - 3.8095i

bus_sol =
    1.0000    1.0260         0    -1.6300    0.3505         0         0         0         0    1.0000
    2.0000    1.0250   24.0078    1.6300    0.3427         0         0         0         0    2.0000

line_flow =
    1.0000    2.0000   -1.6300    0.3505
    2.0000    1.0000    1.6300    0.3427

```

Figure 4.2. Y admittance matrix and power flow solutions

The next step is to initialize the SMIB parameters, the script “SMIB_run.m” in the appendix initializes the SMIB parameters using the machine data’s “mac_con”. It also calls the scripts “Synch_parameter_sys_base” and “generic_Sync_Init” in its program. The former assigns values from the “mac_con” to the different variables of the synchronous machine modeled in chapter three while the latter computes the equations used for the synchronous machine modeled in chapter three as well. The last part of “SMIB_run.m” introduces a fault (three-phase) on the SMIB system by specifying a very large admittance at bus 2 where the generator is connected at 1 second. The uncontrolled generator rotor speed deviation and rotor angle are displayed in Figure 4.3 and Figure 4.4 respectively.

Figure 4.3: Uncontrolled generator rotor speed deviation

Figure 4.4: Uncontrolled generator rotor angle

Using the $[A, B, C, D] = \text{linmod}(\text{'SMIB'})$ command to linearize the system and $[L] = \text{eig}(A)$ to calculate the eigenvalues of the system in Matlab command window Table 4.3 displays eigenvalues while Figure 4.5 shows the eigenvalues plot on the complex S-plane. As seen from the eigenvalue plot mode 1 falls on the right-hand side of the complex S-plane, according to the study [47], if one of the eigenvalues of a system falls on the right-hand side of the complex S-plane, the system is unstable. This instability leads to uncontrolled oscillations as seen in Figure 4.3 and Figure 4.4 respectively.

Table 4.3: Uncontrolled system eigenvalues

NO-PSS	
Mode	Eigenvalues
1	$0.0588 \pm j8.3601, -0.0070$
2	$-13.2994 + j0.000$
3	$-8.8414 + j0.0000$
4	$-3.0673 + j0.0000$

Figure 4.5: Uncontrolled system eigenvalues plot

From Table 4.3, Mode 1 has a corresponding damping ratio of -0.0070. To design the PSS to control the generator rotor speed deviation and angle, the eigenvalue objective function explained in chapter three is adopted, and the PSO, GA, and AEO programs in the appendix are then used optimally to obtain the PSS parameters in Table 4.4. The convergence rate curve for the PSS design of AEO, GA, and PSO is shown in Figure 4.6, the curve shows which optimization technique converged faster in optimal PSS design. From the Figure, AEO converged at iteration 22, PSO at iteration 40, and GA at iteration 32. Thus AEO converged fastest of all the three algorithms.

Figure 4.6. PSS design convergence rate comparing AEO with PSO and GA

Table 4.4. PSS optimal parameters using GA, PSO, and AEO search algorithms

Algorithm	K _{pss}	T1	T2	T3	T4
GA	8.9429	0.5499	0.6597	0.5293	0.0200
PSO	4.6824	0.7697	0.5810	0.5366	0.0201
AEO	39.6109	0.0984	0.0200	0.0949	0.0200

The PSS parameters from Table 4.4 are then used for simulation to provide control for the generator rotor speed and generator rotor angle. Each algorithm performance is compared against each other, Figures 4.7 and 4.8 shows the performances for NO-PSS, GA, PSO, and AEO PSS respectively.

Figure 4.7: Controlled generator rotor speed deviation

Figure 4.8: Controlled generator rotor angle

Also, the performance index from the simulation results above which compares the AEO algorithm with GA and PSO as well as NO-PSS controller as regards the rise time and settling time of the generator rotor speed deviation and rotor angle is shown in Table 4.5.

Table 4.5: SMIB test system performance index

	SMIB							
	Settling time (sec)				Rise Time (sec)			
	No PSS	GA	PSO	AEO	No PSS $\times 10^{-4}$	GA $\times 10^{-6}$	PSO $\times 10^{-6}$	AEO $\times 10^{-6}$
del_{ω}	9.97	2.20	2.15	1.89	1049	0.0154	0.0092	0.0203
s_{δ}	9.99	2.27	2.48	2.73	152	57.4	31.53	89.31

From Table 4.5, del_{ω} the generator rotor speed deviation for the No-PSS controller in the system has a settling time of 9.97 seconds out of 10 seconds which is the simulation time. GA-PSS settles at 2.20 seconds, PSO-PSS at 2.15 seconds and AEO-PSS at 1.89 seconds.

Also for the generator rotor angle s_{δ} , when there was No-PSS controller in the system, the recorded settling time was 9.99 seconds, with 2.27 seconds for the GA-PSS controller 2.48 seconds for PSO-PSS controller and 2.73 seconds for AEO-PSS controller.

In the new operating condition of the SMIB power grid test system eigenvalues with PSS controller modeled on the system. From Table 4.3, Mode 1 which is for the No-PSS damping controller on the system, following an optimal PSS damping controller design and installation, Mode 1 was improved from $0.0588 \pm j8.3601$ to stable mode of $-11.0256 + j12.6091$ for AEO-PSS, $-4.6415 \pm j11.4012$ for GA-PSS and $-4.7259 \pm j9.9642$ for PSO-PSS respectively as shown in Table 4.6 below. Similarly, the mode 1 damping ratio -0.0070 was improved to 0.6583 for AEO-PSS, 0.3771 for GA-PSS, and 0.4285 for PSO-PSS, respectively. Figure 4.9 shows the comparison of eigenvalue plots with an AEO-PSS damping controller and with a No-

PSS damping controller installed on the system. As seen all the eigenvalues for AEO-PSS are on the left-hand side of the complex S-plane which signifies stability in the system.

Table 4.6. SMIB power test system eigenvalue results for the Electromechanical modes for GA, PSO, and AEO-PSS.

Mode	GA-PSS	PSO-PSS	AEO-PSS
1	$-4.6415 \pm j11.4012, 0.3771$	$-4.7259 \pm j9.9642, 0.4285$	$-11.0256 \pm j12.6091, 0.6583$
2	$-4.6435 \pm j5.1892, 0.6668$	$-4.7280 \pm j6.0965, 0.6128$	$-11.0256 \pm j7.2176, 0.8367$
3	$-0.1005 + j0.0000$	$-0.1003 + j0.0000$	$-0.1025 + j0.0000$
4	$-1.5078 + j0.0000$	$-3.2732 + j0.0000$	$-2.1881 + j0.0000$
5	$-3.2179 + j0.0000$	$-1.7255 + j0.0000$	$-8.1633 + j0.0000$

Figure 4.9. AEO-controlled PSS system eigenvalues plot compared to NO-PSS controller

4.3 SMIB integrated with DFIG

The SMIB with DFIG system modeled in Chapter Three is now used for numerical simulations,

Figure 4.10 shows a single-line diagram for SMIB with DFIG. The bus data and line data adopted from [19] and [47] are shown in Tables 4.7 and 4.8.

Figure 4.10: SMIB and DFIG single-line diagram

Tables 4.7. SMIB with DFIG Bus data

Bus NO.,	Voltage	Angle	Pg	Qg	PL	QL	GL	BL	Bus type
1	1.000	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	3
2	1.025	0.00	1.63	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	2
3	1.000	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	3
4	1.025	0.00	0.80	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	2
5	1.040	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1

Table 4.8. SMIB with DFIG Line data

From Bus	To Bus	R	X	B	Tap	Ratio
01	02	0.0625	0.200	0.0000	1.0	0.0
01	05	0.1100	0.100	0.0000	1.0	0.0
03	05	0.0100	0.100	0.0000	1.0	0.0
03	04	0.0370	0.370	0.0000	1.0	0.0

The same procedure for the SMIB test system is utilized here, however, the bus and line data changes as seen in Tables 4.7 and 4.8. the “script for the integrated SMIB and DFIG” uses the new bus and line data to calculate the Y admittance matrix and power flow. It also calls the “SMIB_run” and “find dfig state initial conditions”, these two initialize the SMIB and DFIG parameters respectively. AEO-PSS was designed on the system, Figure 4.11 shows the iteration curve of AEO, which converged to its solution at iteration 48.

Figure 4.11 Iteration curve of AEO

PSS optimal parameters obtained from the design of the AEO-PSS damping controller in the new system are shown in Table 4.9. These parameters were used for simulation and the generator rotor speed deviation response to the simulation is shown in Figure 4.12.

Table 4.9. PSS optimal parameters AEO search algorithm

Algorithm	Kpss	T1	T2	T3	T4
AEO	35.7891	0.9807	0.3943	0.5964	0.8259

Figure 4.12: Generator rotor speed deviation response to AEO-PSS

Also, the performance index from the simulation result above for AEO-PSS as regards the settling time and rise time of the generator rotor speed deviation is shown in Table 4.10

Table 4.10: SMIB test system performance index

AEO-PSS	SMIB with DFIG	
	Settling time(sec)	Rise time(sec)
del_{ω}	2.5	0.0633

From table 4.10, del_{ω} the generator speed deviation for the AEO-PSS controller in the system has a settling time of 2.5 seconds out of 10 seconds which is the simulation time. For the SMIB with the DFIG system, Table 4.11 shows the dominant eigenvalues for the Electromechanical modes for AEO-PSS and the corresponding damping ratio. While Figure 13 shows the eigenvalue plot.

Table 4.11: SMIB with DFIG and PSS damping controller power test system dominant eigenvalue results for the Electromechanical modes for AEO-PSS and the corresponding damping ratio.

Mode	AEO-PSS	Damping ratio
1	$-14.8884 \pm j22.2402$	0.5563
2	$-2.7360 \pm j18.2509$	0.1483
3	$-2.1654 \pm j11.1759$	0.1902
4	$-0.0001 \pm j0.0164$	0.0044

5	$-2.1654 \pm j11.1759$	0.1902
---	------------------------	--------

Figure 4.13. AEO controlled PSS system eigenvalues plot.

Figure 4.13 shows the plot of the eigenvalues for the system with an AEO-PSS damping controller designed and installed on the system. As seen all the eigenvalues are on the left-hand side of the complex S-plane showing the system is stable.

4.4 Conclusion

This chapter presented the results and discussed what the results imply. The conclusions from the study are given in the next chapter. These are based on the results and the discussions.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

This Chapter provides the main findings of this study and the conclusions that can be drawn from each of the objectives of the study. Also, the contribution and suggestions for further study are given so that readers can learn more about the current research. The first goal was to model a single-machine, infinite-bus system and implement the AEO optimization method to design a PSS damping controller for optimal performance. The second objective was to compare the performance of the AEO-PSS damping controller with damping controllers designed using genetic algorithm (GA) and particle swarm optimization (PSO) which are all metaheuristic algorithms and have been adopted in other research works. This was done using non-linear time domain modeling and quantitative analysis. To accomplish the third objective of adding renewable sources of energy to the power system, the DFIG wind energy system was also integrated into SMIB. In the integrated system, A robust AEO-PSS damping controller was proposed. Quantitative analysis and non-linear time-domain simulation results show that the proposed damping controllers reduce electromechanical oscillations and increase the damping ratio of the system.

5.2 Contributions to knowledge

1. Rotor angle stability analysis has been carried out on a single machine connected to an infinite bus system, on the introduction of a fault (three-phase symmetrical) on the system, the generator rotor speed deviation response recorded a settling time of $9.97seconds$ and the response of the generator rotor angle a settling time of $9.99seconds$ out of $10seconds$ (simulation time). The introduction of the PSS damping controller using the AEO

algorithm improved the generator rotor speed settling time to 1.89seconds (81% improvement) and that of the generator rotor angle to 2.73seconds (72% improvement). The installed AEO-PSS damping controller was validated by comparing its performance with damping controllers designed using GA and PSO to prove its robustness.

2. To find an optimal solution to damp the electromechanical oscillations in a single machine connected to an infinite-bus system, the PSS design optimization problem had to be solved. The solution was first obtained by AEO on the 25th iteration, PSO on the 42nd, and GA on the 38th. With the PSS parameters that were obtained, the obtained PSS parameters were able to improve the dominant damping ratio of the single machine infinite bus system with No-PSS damping controller from -0.0070 to 0.6583 for AEO-PSS, 0.3771 to 0.4285 for GA-PSS, and 0.4285 to 0.6583 for PSO-PSS.
3. The single machine connected to an infinite bus system was then modified by incorporating a renewable wind energy source in the form of a doubly-fed induction generator into the system. This introduced renewable wind energy sources to the system.
4. AEO-PSS damping controller was designed on the new system and the generator rotor speed deviation response in terms of settling time was recorded at 2.5seconds out of 10 seconds (simulation time). When compared to the study carried out by Bhukya et al, 2018 [44] after 2.5 seconds the generator rotor speed was not stable, the present study improved the integrated system.

5.3 Recommendations

To further improve this research work, these are the recommendations:

1. The conventional test system can be expanded by adding more generators and buses, which include the three (3) generators, nine (9) bus system known as the western system

coordinating council (WSCC), the ten (10) generators, thirty-nine (39) bus system known as the New England or the four (4) generators two-area, eleven (11) bus test system known as the IEEE Kundur system.

2. Flexible alternating current transmission systems (FACTS) with power oscillation damper (POD) can be introduced to the system or Power system stabilizer (PSS) and FACTS devices coordination like Interline power flow controller (IPFC), Unified power flow controller (UPFC), Static VAR compensator (SVC), Static Compensator (STATCOM) can be introduced to the system to improve the electromechanical damping performance.
3. Fuzzy logic damping controllers and also neural networks like the neuro-fuzzy controller can be introduced to the system as well.
4. Machine learning algorithms can be introduced in the optimal design of the damping controller.

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APPENDIX

```
% The code was provided by L. Kunjumammed (2019).
%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%% function to form Y admittance matrix %%%%%%%%%%
function [Y] = form_Ymatrix(bs,ln);%Takes two inputs 'bs' and 'ln' which are
bus and line data
Y = zeros(size(bs,1),size(bs,1)); %Initialising Y bus matrix to zero
sy = size(Y);%size of Y bus matrix equal to the number of buses in the
%network
% This block of code adds line series admittance and shunt admittance to the
% diagonal elements of Y. First obtain an index of diagonal elements
%corresponding to ln(:,1), sub2ind(linear index from multiple subscripts)
t = sub2ind(sy, ln(:,1), ln(:,1));
% Matrix Kt ensures correct admittance is added when more than one line
% connects two buses unique(to avoid repetitions)
[t1, t2, t3] = unique(t); Kt = zeros(size(t2,1),size(t3,1));
Kt((1:size(Kt,2))-1*size(Kt,1)+t3')=1;
% assigning values to diagonal elements
Y(t1) = Y(t1) + Kt*(1./(ln(:,3)+1i*ln(:,4))+1i*0.5*ln(:,5));
% This block does the same as the previous block, but for the buses in
ln(:,2)
t = sub2ind(sy, ln(:,2), ln(:,2));
[t1, t2, t3] = unique(t); Kt = zeros(size(t2,1),size(t3,1));
Kt((1:size(Kt,2))-1*size(Kt,1)+t3')=1;
Y(t1) = Y(t1) + Kt*(1./(ln(:,3)+1i*ln(:,4))+1i*0.5*ln(:,5));
% This block of codes obtains the indices of the off-diagonal elements
%corresponding to the lines connecting the two buses and then subtracts the
%corresponding admittance values from the corresponding values from the
%corresponding elements of the Y matrix
% obtaining index of off-diagonal elements ln(:,1) to ln(:,2)
t = sub2ind(sy, ln(:,1), ln(:,2));
[t1, t2, t3] = unique(t); Kt = zeros(size(t2,1),size(t3,1));
Kt((1:size(Kt,2))-1*size(Kt,1)+t3')=1;
Y(t1) = Y(t1) - Kt*(1./(ln(:,3)+1i*ln(:,4)));
% obtaining index of off-diagonal elements ln(:,2) to ln(:,1)
t = sub2ind(sy, ln(:,2), ln(:,1));
[t1, t2, t3] = unique(t); Kt = zeros(size(t2,1),size(t3,1));
Kt((1:size(Kt,2))-1*size(Kt,1)+t3')=1;
Y(t1) = Y(t1) - Kt*(1./(ln(:,3)+1i*ln(:,4)));
% Adding shunt admittances at buses in the diagonal elements
Y = Y + diag(bs(:,8) + 1i*bs(:,9));
End

% The code was provided by L. Kunjumammed (2019).
%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%% function to calculate power flow %%%%%%%%%%
function [bus_sln, flow] = power_flow(Y, bs, ln)
% The program solves load flow equations for a power system
bs(:,3) = bs(:,3)*pi/180; % converting angle from degrees to radians
V0 = bs(:,2); A0 = bs(:,3); nbs = size(bs,1);
```

```

bs1 = find(bs(:,10)==1); bpv = find(bs(:,10)==2); ...
    bpq = find(bs(:,10)==3);
% Active and reactive power specified at pv and pQ buses
PQ = [bs(bpv,4)-bs(bpv,6);bs(bpq,4)-bs(bpq,6); bs(bpq,5)-bs(bpq,7)];
% Initial estimate of voltage angle (pv and pQ bus) and magnitude (pQ bus)
vt0 = [bs(sort([bpv;bpq]),3);bs(bpq,2)];
itrn = 1; % the while function iteratively updates the voltage magnitude and
%angle estimates until convergence is achieved. In each iteration, it
%calculates the current and power flows in the power system based on the
%current voltage estimate
while(true)
    % updating voltage magnitude and angle
    T = [zeros(size(bpq,1),size(bpq,1)+size(bpv,1)) ...
eye(size(bpq,1))];
    V0(bpq) = T*vt0;
    T = [eye(size(bpv,1)+size(bpq,1)) ...
zeros(size(bpq,1)+size(bpv,1),size(bpq,1))];
    A0(sort([bpv; bpq])) = T*vt0;
% Calculate voltage, current, and power based on the estimate
    v0 = V0.*exp(1i*A0); i0 = Y*v0; pq0 = v0.*conj(i0);
% Find the difference in active and reactive power
    dpq = PQ-[real(pq0(sort([bpv;bpq])));imag(pq0(sort(bpq)))]];
    K = diag(v0)*conj(Y)*diag(conj(v0)); % Calculating K matrix
% Building Jacobian Matrix from K matrix
    Jp = [imag(K)-diag(imag(pq0)) ...
(real(K)+diag(real(pq0)))/ (ones(nbs,1)*V0')];
    Jq = [diag(real(pq0))-real(K) ...
(imag(K)+diag(imag(pq0)))/ (ones(nbs,1)*V0')];
    J = [Jp;Jq];
    J(sort([bs1; nbs+bs1;nbs+bpv]),:)=[];
    J(:,sort([bs1; nbs+bs1;nbs+bpv]))=[];
    dvt = J\dpq; % Finding change in voltage magnitude and angle
    vt0 = vt0 + dvt; % Updating voltage magnitude and angle
    itrn = itrn + 1;
    if max(abs(dvt))<1e-16 || itrn >50 % the iteration continues until the
%maximum change in voltage magnitude and angle is less than a threshold or
%the maximum iteration limit is reached.
        break
    end
end
end
% Building solved bus matrix
bus_sln = bs;
bus_sln(:,2:3) = [abs(v0) angle(v0)*180/pi];
bus_sln(sort([bpv;bs1]),4:5) = [real(pq0(sort([bpv;bs1]))) ...
imag(pq0(sort([bpv;bs1])))];
% calculating line flow
sln = size(ln,1); flow = zeros(2*sln,4);
t = sub2ind(size(Y), ln(:,1), ln(:,2));
yft = Y(t);
flw = -v0(ln(:,1)).*conj(((v0(ln(:,1))-v0(ln(:,2))).*yft));
flow(1:sln, 1:4) = [ln(:,1) ln(:,2) real(flw) imag(flw)];
flw = -v0(ln(:,2)).*conj(((v0(ln(:,2))-v0(ln(:,1))).*yft));
flow(sln+1:2*sln, 1:4) = [ln(:,2) ln(:,1) real(flw) imag(flw)];

%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%% the script to calculate initialize SMIB parameters %%%%%%%%%
clear All
system_base_mva = 100.0;

```

```

s_f=60; %System frequency in Hz
s_wb=2*pi*s_f;%Base value radial frequency in rad/sec
s_ws=377; %p.u. value of synchronous speed
s_Ka=200;%Static excitation gain
s-Ta=0.02;%Static excitation time constant
% **** Governor Control SYSTEM DATA - not used ****
s_Tg=0.2;% the governor time constant (Kundur p.598)
s_Rgov=0.05;% the governor droop (Kundur p.598)
% Bus No., voltage, Angle, Pg, Qg, Pl, Ql, Gl, Bl, Bus type
bs = [...
1 1.026 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 1;
2 1.025 0.00 1.63 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 2;
];
% From the bus, To bus, R X B tap ratio
ln = [01 02 0 0.2625 0.0000 1.0 0.0];
% Obtain load flow solution
[Y] = form_Ymatrix(bs,ln);
% calculate pre-fault power flow solution
[bus_sol, line_flow] = power_flow(Y,bs, ln);
%MACHINE DATA STARTS
mac_con = [1 900 0.2 0.0025 1.8 0.3 0.25 8 0.03 1.7 0.55 0.25 0.4 0.05 6.5
0];
% MACHINE DATA ENDS
% synchronous machine initialization
Smachs = [1];% buses with synchronous machine
Nbus=size(bs,1); % Number of buses
NSmachs=size(Smachs,1); % Number of synchronous machines
% program to initialize the synchronous machines based on parameters in
'mac_con'
Synch_parameter_sys_base % or_gen_base, depending on the base system we
decide to work in.
generic_Synch_Init
%Calculates the vector of apparent power S injected by the generators for
%each system bus.
PQ = bus_sol(:,4)+1i*bus_sol(:,5);
% Calculate the complex voltage value for all buses.
vol = bus_sol(:,2).*exp(1i*bus_sol(:,3)*pi/180);
% Calculate the complex value of the current injected by the generators at
% each system bus
Icalc = conj(PQ./vol);
% PL and QL are the real and reactive power drawn by loads at all system
% buses.
PL = bus_sol(:,6);
QL = bus_sol(:,7);
%V is the voltage magnitude at all system buses.
V = bus_sol(:,2);
Vinfvec=ones(Nbus,1);
Vinf=Vinfvec.*(bus_sol(2,2)*exp(1i*bus_sol(2,3)*pi/180));
%bus voltage at infinite bus
Zline=ln(3)+1i*ln(4); %R+jx
%Line impedance
% Finding post-fault impedance matrix
% Define post-fault admittance matrix
Yf = Y;
% Apply three-phase fault at bus-2 by specifying very large admittance at
Yf(2,2) = 10000;
% Find post-fault impedance matrix

```

```

Zf = inv(Yf);
s_wr = (s_delta*1/s_wb)+s_ws;

%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
machine_numb = mac_con(:,1);
machine_base_mva=mac_con(:,2);
s_xls=mac_con(:,3).*system_base_mva./machine_base_mva;
%Armature leakage reactance
s_Rs=mac_con(:,4).*system_base_mva./machine_base_mva;
%Armature resistance
s_xd=mac_con(:,5).*system_base_mva./machine_base_mva;
%d axis synchronous reactance
s_xdd=mac_con(:,6).*system_base_mva./machine_base_mva;
%d axis transient reactance
s_xddd=mac_con(:,7).*system_base_mva./machine_base_mva;
%d axis sub-transient reactance
s_Tdod=mac_con(:,8); %d axis open circuit transient time constant
s_Tdodd=mac_con(:,9); %d axis open circuit sub-transient time constant
s_xq=mac_con(:,10).*system_base_mva./machine_base_mva; %q axis synchronous
reactance
s_xqd=mac_con(:,11).*system_base_mva./machine_base_mva; %q axis transient
reactance
s_xqdd=mac_con(:,12).*system_base_mva./machine_base_mva; %q axis sub-
transient reactance
s_Tqod=mac_con(:,13); %q axis open circuit transient time constant
s_Tqodd=mac_con(:,14); %q axis open circuit sub-transient time constant
s_H= mac_con(:,15).*system_base_mva./machine_base_mva; %Inertia constant
s_D=mac_con(:,16).*system_base_mva./machine_base_mva; %Self-damping
s_Rgov = s_Rgov.*system_base_mva./machine_base_mva;
ExpandSmachs= zeros(Nbus,NSmachs);
for counter=1:NSmachs
ExpandSmachs(Smachs(counter),counter)=1;
end
SelectSmachs= zeros(NSmachs,Nbus);
for counter=1:NSmachs
SelectSmachs(counter,Smachs(counter))=1;
end
s_Pg = bus_sol(Smachs,4);%generator real power in machine base
s_Qg = bus_sol(Smachs,5);%generator reactive power in machine base

%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
generic_Synch.Init.m %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
s_f=60; %System frequency in Hz
s_wb=2*pi*s_f; %Base value radial frequency in rad/sec
s_ws=377; %p.u. value of synchronous speed
Zg= s_Rs + li*s_xddd; %Zg for sub-transient model
Yg=1./Zg; %Yg for sub-transient model
s_volt = bus_sol(Smachs,2); %voltage magnitude generator bus
s_theta = bus_sol(Smachs,3)*pi/180; %voltage angle in rad/sec
s_Vg = s_volt.*(cos(s_theta) + li*sin(s_theta));
%generator terminal voltage in a complex form in the DQ frame
s_Ig = conj((s_Pg+li*s_Qg)./s_Vg);
%current at generator terminal in a complex form in DQ reference
s_Eq = s_Vg + (s_Rs+li.*s_xq).*s_Ig;
%Effective internal voltage defined as shown
s_delta = angle(s_Eq);
%Generator rotor angle

```

```

s_id = -abs(s_Ig) .* (sin(s_delta - angle(s_Ig)));
s_iq = abs(s_Ig) .* cos(s_delta - angle(s_Ig));
s_vd = -abs(s_Vg) .* (sin(s_delta - angle(s_Vg)));
s_vq = abs(s_Vg) .* cos(s_delta - angle(s_Vg));
%converting quantities from DQ-frame to dq-frame(6)
s_Efd = abs(s_Eq) - (s_xd-s_xq).*s_id;
%Initial value for field voltage, to follow detailed
%derivation consult (padiyar k. R., 2008)
s_Eqd = s_Efd + (s_xd-s_xdd).*s_id;
%Derived from (11) and (14)
s_Edd = -(s_xq-s_xqd).*s_iq;
%Derived from (12) and (13)
s_Psild=s_Eqd+(s_xdd-s_xls).*s_id;
%Derived from(14)
s_Psi2q=-s_Edd+(s_xqd-s_xls).*s_iq;
%Derived from(13)
s_Te = s_Eqd.*s_iq.*(s_xddd-s_xls)./(s_xdd-s_xls)+s_Psild.*s_iq.*(s_xdd-
s_xddd)./(s_xdd-s_xls) + s_Edd.*s_id.*(s_xqdd-s_xls)./(s_xqd-s_xls)-
s_Psi2q.*s_id.*(s_xqd-s_xqdd)./(s_xqd-s_xls)-s_iq.*s_id.*(s_xqdd-s_xddd);
%This is (8)
s_wr = (s_delta * (1/s_wb)) + s_ws;
s_Tm=s_Te;
%Derived from (4)
s_iQ = cos(s_delta).*s_iq - sin(s_delta).*s_id;
s_iD = sin(s_delta).*s_iq + cos(s_delta).*s_id;
%Conversion from dq-frame to DQ-frame (7)
s_Vref=s_volt+1./s_Ka.*s_Efd;
%Derived from (3)

%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%% find_dfig_state_initial_conditions %%%%%%%%%
%STEP 2 BEGINS: Gather machine parameters for DFIG
d_welb = 2*pi*50; % electrical base speed rad/sec
d_ws = 377; % Synchronous speed in pu
% DFIG parameters
% data_DF = [mac# bus# d_Lm d_Rs d_Rr d_Lss d_Lrr d_Kopt d_Ktg d_ctg d_Ht
% d_Hg BaseMVA]
data_DF = [1 5 4 0.005 0.0055 4.04 4.0602 1 0.3 0.01 4 0.4 5];
% DFIG-Filter parameters
% FLTR = [d_Ri, d_Rg, d_Rc, d_Li, d_Lg, d_Cf];
d_FLTR = [0.000, 0.000, 0.7333, 0.1667, 0.0033, 0.0150];
d_Cdc = 2; % Converter capacitor
% DFIG-MSc Controller Parameters
d_MSC_IL1_Kp = -0.23;d_MSC_IL1_Ki = -3;
d_MSC_IL2_Kp = -0.23;d_MSC_IL2_Ki = -3; d_MSC_OL1_Kp = 0;d_MSC_OL1_Ki = -60;
d_MSC_OL2_Kp = 0;d_MSC_OL2_Ki = 90;
% DFIG-GSC Controller Parameters
d_GSC_IL1_Kp = 0.3; d_GSC_IL1_Ki = 200; d_GSC_IL2_Kp = 0.3; d_GSC_IL2_Ki =
200; d_GSC_OL1_Kp = -22; d_GSC_OL1_Ki = -870;d_GSC_OL2_Kp = 0;
d_GSC_OL2_Ki = -60;
% Read filter parameters from FLTR vector
d_Ri = 0.0; d_Rg = 0.0; d_Rc = d_FLTR(3);
d_Li = d_FLTR(4); d_Lg = d_FLTR(5); d_Cf = d_FLTR(6);
% Read machine data from data_DF
d_Lm = data_DF(3); d_Xm = d_Lm;
d_Rs = data_DF(4); % stator resistance
d_Rr = data_DF(5); % rotor resistance
d_Lss = data_DF(6); % stator self inductance

```

```

d_Lrr = data_DF(7); % rotor inductance
d_Kopt = data_DF(8); d_Ktg = data_DF(9);
d_ctg = data_DF(10); d_Ht = data_DF(11);
d_Hg = data_DF(12); d_base = data_DF(13);
d_bl = 40.05; % blade length
d_wtrated = 3.0337; % rated turbine speed
rho = 1.225; % air density
% Calculating derived variable
d_Ls_d = d_Lss - (d_Lm^2/d_Lrr);
d_Kmrr = d_Lm/d_Lrr; d_R2 = d_Kmrr^2*d_Rr;
d_R1 = d_Rs + d_R2; d_Tr = d_Lrr/d_Rr;
% STEP 2 ENDS
% STEP 3 BEGINS: Initialization of state variables for generator, converter
% and Filter
Vdfig = bus_sln(Dmachs,2).*exp(1i*bus_sln(Dmachs,3)*pi/180);
Pdfig = bus_sln(Dmachs, 4); Qdfig = bus_sln(Dmachs, 5);
d_vsq = real(Vdfig); d_vsd = imag(Vdfig); d_Theta = angle(Vdfig);
xdfig = zeros(size(Dmachs,1),15); d_isq = xdfig(:,1); d_isd = xdfig(:,2);
d_irq = xdfig(:,3); d_ird = xdfig(:,4); d_vrq = xdfig(:,5);
d_vrd = xdfig(:,6); d_iiq = xdfig(:,7); d_iid = xdfig(:,8);
d_igq = xdfig(:,9); d_igd = xdfig(:,10); d_viq = xdfig(:,11); d_vid =
xdfig(:,12); d_vdq = xdfig(:,13); d_vcd = xdfig(:,14); d_wg = xdfig(:,15);
% d_esq and d_esd are calculated using (24)
d_esq = d_Kmrr.*d_ws.*(d_Lrr.*d_ird + d_Lm.*d_isd);
d_esd = -d_Kmrr.*d_ws.*(d_Lrr.*d_irq + d_Lm.*d_isq);
%***** STEP 4 BEGINS: Initialization of converter controllers and
%turbine *****
% Parameters for RSC controller model
d_vr_dash = (d_vrq+1i*d_vrd).*exp(-1i*d_Theta);
d_ir_dash = (d_irq+1i*d_ird).*exp(-1i*d_Theta);
d_MSC_IL1_iv = real(d_vr_dash); d_MSC_IL2_iv = imag(d_vr_dash);
d_MSC_OL1_iv = real(d_ir_dash); d_MSC_OL2_iv = imag(d_ir_dash);
d_Qs = Qdfig; % Reactive power reference RSC controller
% B2B capacitor
d_VDC = 1.5;
% Parameters for GSC controller model
d_vi_dash = (d_viq+1i*d_vid).*exp(-1i*d_Theta);
d_ii_dash = (d_igq+1i*d_igd).*exp(-1i*d_Theta);
d_GSC_IL1_iv = real(d_vi_dash); d_GSC_IL2_iv = imag(d_vi_dash);
d_GSC_OL1_iv = real(d_ii_dash); d_GSC_OL2_iv = imag(d_ii_dash);
d_Qfilter = 0; % Reactive power reference GSC controller
% Turbine initialization
d_Tg = d_esq.*d_isq+d_esd.*d_isd; d_Ts = d_Tg; d_wt = d_wg; d_Pt =
d_Ts.*d_wt;
% Values associated with turbine
rho = 1.225;
d_wtrated = 3.0337; d_wt = 0.9688; d_wg = 0.9688;
d_bl = 40.0595545; d_Lambda = 8.1;
d_Beta = 0; d_vw = 14.5316; d_Ts = 0.9386;
d_base = 5.0009990; d_welb = 2*pi*50; d_Tg=d_Ts; d_wb = 2*pi*50;
d_w = 2*pi*50;

%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%% Script for the integrated SMIB and DFIG system %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
% Bus No., voltage, Angle, Pg, Qg, Pl, Ql, Gl, Bl, Bus type
bs = [...
01 1.000 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 3;
02 1.025 0.00 1.63 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 2;

```

```

03 1.000 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 3;
04 1.025 0.00 0.80 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 2;
05 1.040 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 0.00 1;
];
% From the bus, To bus, R X B tap ratio
ln = [01 02 0.0625 0.20 0.000 1.0 0.0;
      01 05 0.1100 0.10 0.000 1.0 0.0;
      03 05 0.0100 0.10 0.000 1.0 0.0;
      03 04 0.0370 0.37 0.000 1.0 0.0;];
% obtain load flow solution
Y = form_Ymatrix(bs,ln);
% calculate power flow solution
[bus_sln, line_flow] = power_flow(Y,bs, ln);
Znet = inv(Y);
vinf = bus_sln(3,2)*exp(1i*bus_sln(3,3)*pi/180);
ZA = Znet(1:end-1,1:end-1); ZB = Znet(1:end-1,end);
ZC = Znet(end,1:end-1); ZD = Znet(end,end); % Znet = [ZA ZB; ZC ZD]
%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
Smachs = [2]'; % Bus where SMIB is connected
Dmachs = [4]'; % Bus where DFIG is connected
Omega = 2*pi*50;
if size(Smachs,1)
    SMIB_run
    smib_mult = zeros(size(bus_sln,1)-1,size(Smachs,1));
    smib_mult(Smachs,:) = eye(size(Smachs,1));
end
if size(Dmachs,1)
    find_dfig_state_initial_conditions
    dfig_mult = zeros(size(bus_sln,1)-1,size(Dmachs,1));
    dfig_mult(Dmachs,:) = eye(size(Dmachs,1));
end
d_vw = 14.5316; d_Lm = 4; d_Rs = 0.005; d_Rr = 0.0055;
d_Lss = 4.04; d_Lrr = 4.0602; d_Kopt =1; d_ktg = 0.3;
d_ctg = 0.01; d_Ht = 4; d_Hg = 0.4;
d_ws =377; d_Tg=d_Ts; d_wb = 2*pi*50;
d_w = 2*pi*50; d_vcq = 0.9837;
d_MSC_IL1_kp = -0.23; d_MSC_IL1_ki = -3; d_MSC_IL1_iv = 0.0389;
d_MSC_IL2_kp = -0.23; d_MSC_OL1_kp = 0; d_MSC_OL2_kp = 0;
d_GSC_IL1_kp = 0.3; d_GSC_IL2_kp = 0.3; d_GSC_OL1_kp = -22;
d_GSC_OL2_kp = 0; SelectSmachs = [1]; ExpandSmachs = [1];

%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%% Function for AEO %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
%% This code was provided by reference 29
function [BestX,BestF,HisBestFit]=MyAEO(F_index,MaxIt,nPop)
% BestX: The best solution found so far, BestF: The best fitness
corresponding to BestX.
% HisBestFit: History best fitness over iterations.
% MaxIt: The maximum number of iterations.
% D: The decomposition factor.
[Low,Up,Dim]=PssRange(F_index);% F_index: Index of function, Low and Up: The
lower and upper bound of search space.
PopPos=zeros(nPop,Dim);% PopPos: The position of population, Dim: The
dimensionality of the problem.
PopFit=zeros(1,nPop);% PopFit: The fitness of the population,nPop: The size
of the population.
for i=1:nPop

```

```

    PopPos(i,:) = rand(1, Dim) .* (Up - Low) + Low;
    PopFit(i) = pss_objf(PopPos(i,:), F_index, Dim);
end
[~, indF] = sort(PopFit, 'descend');
PopPos = PopPos(indF, :);
PopFit = PopFit(indF);
BestF = PopFit(end);
BestX = PopPos(end, :);
HisBestFit = zeros(MaxIt, 1);
Matr = [1, Dim];
for It = 1:MaxIt
    r1 = rand;
    a = (1 - It/MaxIt) * r1;
    xrand = rand(1, Dim) .* (Up - Low) + Low;
    newPopPos(1, :) = (1 - a) * PopPos(nPop, :) + a * xrand; % Production
process:equation (25)
    u = randn(1, Dim);
    v = randn(1, Dim);
    C = 1/2 * u ./ abs(v); %equation (26), C: The consumption factor.
    newPopPos(2, :) = PopPos(2, :) + C .* (PopPos(2, :) - newPopPos(1, :));
    for i = 3:nPop
        u = randn(1, Dim);
        v = randn(1, Dim);
        C = 1/2 * u ./ abs(v);
        r = rand;
        if r < 1/3
            newPopPos(i, :) = PopPos(i, :) + C .* (PopPos(i, :) - newPopPos(1, :));
%equation (3.27)
        else
            if 1/3 < r && r < 2/3
                newPopPos(i, :) = PopPos(i, :) + C .* (PopPos(i, :) - PopPos(randi([2
i-1]), :)); %equation (3.28)
            else
                r2 = rand;
                newPopPos(i, :) = PopPos(i, :) + C .* (r2 .* (PopPos(i, :) -
newPopPos(1, :)) + (1 - r2) .* (PopPos(i, :) - PopPos(randi([2 i-1]), :))); %equation
(3.30)
            end
        end
    end
end
for i = 1:nPop
    newPopPos(i, :) = SpaceBound(newPopPos(i, :), Up, Low);
    newPopFit(i) = pss_objf(newPopPos(i, :), F_index, Dim);
    if newPopFit(i) < PopFit(i)
        PopFit(i) = newPopFit(i);
        PopPos(i, :) = newPopPos(i, :);
    end
end
[~, indOne] = min(PopFit);
for i = 1:nPop
    r3 = rand; Ind = round(rand) + 1;
    newPopPos(i, :) = PopPos(indOne, :) + 3 * randn(1, Matr(Ind)) .* ((r3 * randi([1
2]) - 1) * PopPos(indOne, :) - (2 * r3 - 1) * PopPos(i, :)); %equation (53)
end
for i = 1:nPop
    newPopPos(i, :) = SpaceBound(newPopPos(i, :), Up, Low);
    newPopFit(i) = pss_objf(newPopPos(i, :), F_index, Dim);

```

```

        if newPopFit(i)<PopFit(i)
            PopPos(i,:)=newPopPos(i,:);
            PopFit(i)=newPopFit(i);
        end
    end
    [~,indF]=sort(PopFit,'descend');
    PopPos=PopPos(indF,:);
    PopFit=PopFit(indF);
    if PopFit(end)<BestF
        BestF=PopFit(end);
        BestX=PopPos(end,:);
    end
    HisBestFit(It)=BestF;
    display(['Iteration ' num2str(It) ': HisBestF = '
num2str(HisBestFit(It))]);
end

%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%% Script for PSO %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
%% source:https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sB1n9a9yxJk&t=4s
%% Publisher: Yarpiz (https://www.yarpiz.com)
%% Instructor: Mostapha Kalami Heris
clc;
clear;
close all;
%% Problem Definition
CostFunction=@pss_objf;
nVar=5; % Number of Decision Variables
VarSize=[1 nVar]; % Size of Decision Variables Matrix
VarMin=[0.001,0.001,0.02,0.001,0.02]; % Lower Bound of Variables
VarMax=[50,1,1,1,1]; % Upper Bound of Variables
%% Parameters of PSO
MaxIt=100; % Maximum Number of Iterations
nPop=100; % Population Size (Swarm Size)
w=1; % Inertia Weight
wdamp=0.99; % Inertia Weight Damping Ratio
c1=1.5; % Personal Learning Coefficient
c2=2.0; % Global Learning Coefficient
% Velocity Limits
VelMax=0.1*(VarMax-VarMin);
VelMin=-VelMax;
%% Initialization
% The Particle Template
empty_particle.Position=[];
empty_particle.Cost=[];
empty_particle.Velocity=[];
empty_particle.Best.Position=[];
empty_particle.Best.Cost=[];
% Create Population Array
particle= repmat(empty_particle,nPop,1);
% Intialize Global best
GlobalBest.Cost = inf;
%% Initialize Population Members
for i=1:nPop
    % Generate Random Solution
    particle(i).Position=unifrnd(VarMin,VarMax,VarSize);
    % Initialize Velocity
    particle(i).Velocity=zeros(VarSize);
end

```

```

    % Evaluation
    particle(i).Cost=CostFunction(particle(i).Position);
    % Update the Personal Best
    particle(i).Best.Position=particle(i).Position;
    particle(i).Best.Cost=particle(i).Cost;
    % Update Global Best
    if particle(i).Best.Cost<GlobalBest.Cost
        GlobalBest=particle(i).Best;
    end
end
% Array to Hold Best Cost Value of Each Iteration
BestCost=zeros(MaxIt,1);
%% Main Loop of PSO
for it=1:MaxIt
    for i=1:nPop
        % Update Velocity
        particle(i).Velocity = w*particle(i).Velocity ...
            +c1*rand(VarSize).*(particle(i).Best.Position-
particle(i).Position) ...
            +c2*rand(VarSize).*(GlobalBest.Position-particle(i).Position);
        % Apply Velocity Limits
        particle(i).Velocity = max(particle(i).Velocity,VelMin);
        particle(i).Velocity = min(particle(i).Velocity,VelMax);
        % Update Position
        particle(i).Position = particle(i).Position + particle(i).Velocity;
        % Velocity Mirror Effect
        IsOutside=(particle(i).Position<VarMin |
particle(i).Position>VarMax);
        particle(i).Velocity(IsOutside)=-particle(i).Velocity(IsOutside);
        % Apply Position Limits
        particle(i).Position = max(particle(i).Position,VarMin);
        particle(i).Position = min(particle(i).Position,VarMax);
        % Evaluation
        particle(i).Cost = CostFunction(particle(i).Position);
        % Update Personal Best
        if particle(i).Cost<particle(i).Best.Cost
            particle(i).Best.Position=particle(i).Position;
            particle(i).Best.Cost=particle(i).Cost;
            % Update Global Best
            if particle(i).Best.Cost<GlobalBest.Cost
                GlobalBest=particle(i).Best;
            end
        end
    end
    end
    BestCost(it)=GlobalBest.Cost;
    disp(['Iteration ' num2str(it) ': Best Cost = ' num2str(BestCost(it))]);
    w=w*wdamp;
end
BestSol = GlobalBest;
%% Results
figure;
semilogy(BestCost,'LineWidth',2);
xlabel('No. of Iterations');
ylabel('PSS Design Index');
grid on;

```

```

%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%% Script for GA %%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%

```

```

%% source: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ICzcG0ORv6I
%% Publisher: Yarpiz (https://www.yarpiz.com)
%% Instructor: Mostapha Kalami Heris
function out = RunGA(problem, params)
% Problem
CostFunction = problem.CostFunction;
nVar = problem.nVar;
VarSize = [1, nVar];
VarMin = problem.VarMin;
VarMax = problem.VarMax;
% Params
MaxIt = params.MaxIt;
nPop = params.nPop;
beta = params.beta;
pC = params.pC;
nC = round(pC*nPop/2)*2;
gamma = params.gamma;
mu = params.mu;
sigma = params.sigma;
% Template for Empty Individuals
empty_individual.Position = [];
empty_individual.Cost = [];
% Best Solution Ever Found
bestsol.Cost = inf;
% Initialization
pop = repmat(empty_individual, nPop, 1);
for i = 1:nPop
    % Generate Random Solution
    pop(i).Position = unifrnd(VarMin, VarMax, VarSize);
    % Evaluate Solution
    pop(i).Cost = CostFunction(pop(i).Position);
    % Compare Solution to Best Solution Ever Found
    if pop(i).Cost < bestsol.Cost
        bestsol = pop(i);
    end
end
% Best Cost of Iterations
bestcost = nan(MaxIt, 1);
% Main Loop
for it = 1:MaxIt
    % Selection Probabilities
    c = [pop.Cost];
    avgc = mean(c);
    if avgc ~= 0
        c = c/avgc;
    end
    probs = exp(-beta*c);
    % Initialize Offsprings Population
    popc = repmat(empty_individual, nC/2, 2);
    % Crossover
    for k = 1:nC/2
        % Select Parents
        p1 = pop(RouletteWheelSelection(probs));
        p2 = pop(RouletteWheelSelection(probs));
        % Perform Crossover
        [popc(k, 1).Position, popc(k, 2).Position] = ...
            UniformCrossover(p1.Position, p2.Position, gamma);
    end
end
end

```

```

end
% Convert popc to Single-Column Matrix
popc = popc(:);
% Mutation
for l = 1:nC
    % Perform Mutation
    popc(l).Position = Mutate(popc(l).Position, mu, sigma);
    % Check for Variable Bounds
    popc(l).Position = max(popc(l).Position, VarMin);
    popc(l).Position = min(popc(l).Position, VarMax);
    % Evaluation
    popc(l).Cost = CostFunction(popc(l).Position);
    % Compare Solution to Best Solution Ever Found
    if popc(l).Cost < bestsol.Cost
        bestsol = popc(l);
    end
end
% % Merge and Sort Population
pop = SortPopulation([pop; popc]);
% Remove Extra Individuals
pop = pop(1:nPop);
% Update Best Cost of Iteration
bestcost(it) = bestsol.Cost;
% Display Iteration Information
disp(['Iteration ' num2str(it) ': Best Cost = '
num2str(bestcost(it))]);
end
% Results
out.pop = pop;
out.bestsol = bestsol;
out.bestcost = bestcost;
end

%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%% To perform rotor angle stability analysis %%%%%%%%%
Initialising_SMIB_DFIG
% x is the Lead-Lag PSS parameters from optimization.
x = [35.7891    0.980681    0.394337    0.596368    0.825971];
KG = x(1);
Tw = 10;
T1 = x(2);
T2 = x(3);
T3 = x(4);
T4 = x(5);
Kpss = KG*T1*T3/(T2*T4);
%% Linearize Power System
%f11=linmod('SMIB_with_PSS')
f11=linmod('SMIB_with_DFIG_PSS');
Asys = f11.a ;
Bsys = f11.b ;
Csys = f11.c ;
Dsys = f11.d ;
%% Calculate Eigenvalues
egs = eig(Asys)
Ns = length(egs);
Damp = -real(egs) ./sqrt(real(egs).^2+imag(egs).^2)
freq = abs(imag(egs))/(2*pi)

```